

Development of methodics and modeling system of nitrogen and phosphorus load calculation for surface waters of Lithuania
ID Nr.100054

The 2nd Interim Report by
UAB „Estonian, Latvian & Lithuanian Environment” and
SIA „Procesu analīzes un izpētes centrs”

Client: Aplinkos Apsaugos Agentūra

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Procesu analīzes un izpētes centrs

APLINKOS APSAUGOS AGENTŪRA

“AZOTO IR FOSFORO BALANSO IR SUSILAIKYMO SKAIČIAVIMO METODIKŲ BEI PASIŪLYMŲ VANDENS TELKINIŲ APKROVOS TERŠALAIS SKAIČIAVIMO LIETUVOS METODIKAI PARENGIMAS BEI LIETUVOS SITUACIJOS PAGAL PARENGTAS METODIKAS ĮVERTINIMAS“ (PIRKIMO NR. 100054)

the Project is co-financed
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The 2nd Interim Report

by

**UAB “Estonian, Latvian & Lithuanian Environment” (ELLE)
and
SIA “Procesu analīzes un izpētes centrs” (PAIC)**

October 2012

Approved by:

Aplinkos apsaugos agentūra		
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Date:	Date	
Signature:	Signature:	

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1 Introduction

The overall objective of the project “Development of methodics and modelling system of nitrogen and phosphorus load calculation for surface waters of Lithuania” is the assessment of nitrogen and phosphorus budget by means of the development and subsequent application of the surface water quality modelling system (or model) for the physical territory of Lithuania; use of diffuse semi-parametric model(s) to assess the situation in Lithuania using the simulation system developed (or model) and the integration of the developed simulation system (or model) with the other water models of the Environmental Protection Agency of the Ministry of Environment of the Republic of Lithuania.

The main objective is to meet the requirements of Water Framework Directive and the recommendations of the Helsinki Convention regarding the surface water quality and loads of nutrients into the Baltic Sea.

Lithuanian water quality authorities require efficient and reliable water management, evaluation and forecasting tools to comply with Lithuania’s commitments to achieve good water status by 2015 and contribute to the Baltic Sea restoration of good ecological status by 2021. Such tools are water quality modelling systems, which not only allow forecasting of effects of pollution abatement programmes, extreme situations and accidents, but also to evaluate climate change effects on water ecosystems. Implementation and application of such systems are necessary to make sound water management decisions.

Specific objectives of the project are:

1. Select and prepare modelling system (or model) suitable for the modelling nutrient load, retention and concentration of water quality elements such as total nitrogen, total phosphorus, nitrates, ammonium, phosphates, BOD7, dissolved oxygen and sediments;
2. Calculate yearly nutrient loads to water bodies, retention in water bodies and nutrient load apportionment between different sources for the time period of 2000 to 2010 for the Lithuanian territory using modelling system (or model) prepared under the first objective;
3. Prepare GIS based Decision Support Method (DSM) for the identification of critical source areas of nutrient loads and sensitive areas for nitrates;
4. Integrate modelling system (model) prepared under the first objective with the Agency’s prepared MIKE 11 model for the main Lithuania’s rivers;
5. Integrate modelling system (model) prepared for objective 4 with MIKE 21 model of the Curonian Lagoon and the Baltic Sea Coast.

The project commenced on May 31, 2011. Total duration of the project is 16 months.

The project is implemented by SIA “Procesu analizes un izpetes centrs” (PAIC) in partnership with UAB “Estonian, Latvian & Lithuanian Environment”.

First Interim Report was prepared after first 5 months of the project implementation and after round of comments approved by the Project Steering Committee on April 10, 2012. According to the working plan the first reporting phase of the project has covered the following activities from A1 to A5 in accordance of the Task 1 as defined in the Contract:

- A1 – Selection of the appropriate modelling system
- A2 – Definition of input data sets and mobilization of data
- A3 – Model set-up and calibration for the selected pilot basins
- A4 – Validation sensitivity and uncertainty analysis
- A5 – Model setup and calibration for Lithuania

Whereas the 2nd Interim Report which is submitted in time based the revised time schedule for the delivery of the report (letter of the Agency No. (10)-A4-1005 of April 10, 2012). This Report covers:

- Task 2. Application of the developed modelling system for calculation of water quality for the time period 2000-2010 (activities A8-A11); and
- Task 3. Development of the GIS-based decision support system (DSS) (activities A12-A14).

More detailed description of progress achieved under each activity of each task is provided in the Chapter 2.2 “Activities carried out during the second reporting period”.

2 Implementation of the Project

2.1. Organisational setup of the project

The project team consists of employees of the consulting Consortium members SIA “Procesu analizes un izpētes centrs” (PAIC) in partnership with UAB “Estonian, Latvian & Lithuanian Environment”.

The project administration and management from the Consortium side is organized by the Project Working Group (WG), which consists of the Project Manager Dr. Uldis Bethers (PAIC) and partner’s responsible person for the communication, reporting, data collection Aidas Pivoriūnas (UAB „ELLE“). Since July 16, 2012 Aidas Pivoriūnas responsibilities have been taken over by Viktorija Maceikaitė who replaced him in UAB “ELLE”.

Project scientific leader is Dr. Agrita Briede (PAIC), but the main modelling expert is Juris Senņikovs (PAIC). The WG has developed the project management scheme, coordinate all team work, approve tasks for experts, control and adjust the relevant issues, including the compliance with the time schedule, reporting and quality assurance.

Project implementation is monitored by the Project Supervision Committee (SC) established by the Agency. The tasks of the SC include evaluation and approval of intermediate and final project reports, initiation of deployment of sanctions, if any breach is noticed in the project implementation schedule, initiation of changes in project activities, monitoring and evaluation of the implementation and achievement of project objectives, provision of recommendations in order to ensure effective implementation of the project.

Whereas seeking to facilitate technical project implementation, a Project Implementation Group (IG) was formed during the kick-off meeting on 9th of May, 2011. The Agency appointed following representatives to the IG:

- Rasa Maslauskaitė, Project Manager from Agency’s side, Head of Project Management and Public Procurement Unit;
- Svajūnas Plungė, the leading Technical Coordinator, Chief Specialist and Watershed Modeller;
- Audrius Šepikas, Chief Specialist

The Project IG has frequent technical meetings starting from June 2011. UAB "ELLE" is responsible for preparation of minutes of such meetings that are distributed to Uldis Bethers and Svajūnas Plungė. Official agreed language of technical meetings and minutes of the meetings is English. In the second reporting period two technical meetings were organized on May-3 and Jul-27, 2012 (minutes of the meetings attached in Annexes 1, 2). The comments of EPA on the Draft version of the 2nd Interim report were discussed on Aug-27, 2012.

2.2. Activities carried out during the second reporting period

During the second period of the project implementation the following objectives were addressed and activities performed (according to Technical specifications):

1. The modelling system developed in ELLE&PAIC (2012a) was enhanced, see section 2.2.1.
2. The water quality modelling system was used for calculation of yearly nutrient loads to water bodies, retention in water bodies and nutrient load apportionment between different sources for the time period of 2000 to 2010 for the Lithuania territory (objective 2.2.2), including the following activities:
 - a. The methodology for the separation of background, non-point agricultural sources and other anthropogenic pollution sources is prepared in Section 2.2.2 (activity 2.4.1.1).
 - b. The yearly nutrient loads (from different sources such as background, non-point agricultural pollution, point sources and international pollution) to the surface water bodies of Lithuanian river basin districts for time period of 2000-2010 are calculated and presented in Section 2.2.3 (activity 2.4.1.2).
 - c. The nutrient retention in the surface water bodies of Lithuanian river basin districts for 2000-2010 year period are calculated in Section 2.2.4 (activity 2.4.1.3).
 - d. The methodology for the calculation of source apportionment of riverine loads of the loads to the Baltic Sea was developed in Section 2.2.5 (activity 2.4.1.4).
 - e. The source apportionment of riverine loads of loads coming to the Baltic Sea for the time period of 2000-2010 is calculated by using prepared methodology in Section 2.2.6 (activity 2.4.1.5).
 - f. The methodology for the normalization of the nutrient loads by eliminating the influence of hydrometeorological factors (weather and water flows) is recommended and developed in Section 2.2.7 (activity 2.4.1.6).
 - g. The normalized nutrient load to the Baltic Sea for the period of 2000-2010 is calculated in Section 2.2.8 (activity 2.4.1.7).
 - h. The evaluation of the results of the calculation of loads to surface water bodies, retention, loads to Baltic Sea, their apportionment and normalization is given in respective Sections – 2.2.3, 2.2.4, 2.2.6 and 2.2.8 (activity 2.4.1.8). The set of methodologies in Sections 2.2.2, 2.2.5 and 2.2.7 form a technical manual for the calculation of nutrient load, retention, source apportionment of riverine loads and load normalization (activity 2.4.1.9).
 - i. The recommendations for the future development of modeling system and methods in regard to the calculation of nutrient load, retention, source apportionment of riverine loads and load normalization (activity 2.4.1.10) are given in concluding remarks (Chapter 3).
3. The GIS based Decision Support Method (DSM) for the identification of critical source areas of nutrient loads and sensitive areas for nitrates was prepared (objective 2.2.3) including the following activities:

- a. GIS DSM to identify critical nutrient source areas, sensitive nitrate areas and the respective technical documentation for prepared methods is given in Section 2.2.9 (activity 2.5.1.1).
- b. GIS layer (at a scale of 1:50000) and maps of critical nutrient source areas and nitrate sensitive areas are prepared by using GIS DSM methodology (activity 2.5.1.2). They are included in electronic deliverable and Annex III.
- c. The recommendations for the future application and development of GIS DSM methodology are given in Section 2.2.10.

2.2.1. Improvement of modeling system

The water quality modelling system for the territory of Lithuania was developed in ELLE & PAIC (2012a, b). There were several improvements included in the modelling system during the Stage II of the project:

1. The logistics of transboundary water and nutrients inputs was implemented in PAIC SWAT software. The functionality of the PAIC SWAT will be described in the software user manual in Stage III.
2. The automated data transfer between hierarchical setup system ELLE & PAIC (2012a) and automatic recalculation for the whole (or part of) territory of Lithuania was implemented in PAIC SWAT software. The functionality of the PAIC SWAT will be described in the software user manual in Stage III.
3. The hierarchical system of setups was revised, see Table 1 which corresponds to the set of setups transferred electronically with this report. The Table replaces Table 20 of ELLE & PAIC (2012a).
4. GUI was added to PAIC SWAT system. The functionality of the PAIC SWAT will be described in the software user manual in Stage III.
5. The reconsideration of the regionalisation was performed. 19 regions (Table 2) were selected and 19 sets of coefficients attributed to the setups with similar characteristics. The regionalisation was initially based on the MIKE BASIN regionalisation provided by EPA.
6. The re-calibration of the modelling system was performed aiming at
 - a. Better processes description, e.g. in regions which were firstly calculated after the resolving of transboundary issues and where the results were unsatisfactory due to low spring-flood maximum (Žeimena, Merkys).
 - b. Achievement of reasonable agreement of modelling results and observations at downstream monitoring stations. As an example see Figs. 1-6 for the time-graphs – comparison of modelled and observed discharge and main nutrients loads at Nemunas Smalininkai station. The NSE and PBias for these graphs are given in Table 3. The comparison indicates good agreement. Note that the modeled loads (on daily basis) exceed observed loads (on monthly basis) for N-NH₄ only at the peak values. An issue is briefly discussed in the report.
7. The enhancement of the performance of the modelling system will be continued during Stage III of the project.

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The set of regionalised SWAT co-efficients after calibration are summarised in Table 2. This Table replaces Table 26 of ELLE & PAIC (2012a). The values expressed as “%” indicate the difference from the default coefficient value which is determined by either SWAT default values or methodics in ELLE & PAIC (2012a). Table 2 contains indicative regional values of the coefficients – the calibrated coefficient values are supplied electronically with the update of the water quality modelling system.

Table 1. The list of watershed setups for the territory of Lithuania.

Basin	SWAT Watershed	Setup (Directory)
Bartuva	Apšė	Bartuva/Apse
Bartuva	Bartuva	Bartuva/Bartuva_Skuodas
Dauguva	497	Dauguva/497
Dauguva	514	Dauguva/514
Dauguva	Birvėta	Dauguva/Bivyte
Dauguva	Drūkša	Dauguva/Drukša
Dauguva	Dysna	Dauguva/Dysna
Dauguva	Lukšta	Dauguva/Ilukste
Dauguva	Laukesa	Dauguva/Laukesa
Dauguva	Rauda	Dauguva/Rauda
Dauguva	Raukuta	Dauguva/Raukuta
Dubysa	Dubysa	Dubysa/Dubysa
Jūra	Ežeruona	Jura/Ezeruona
Jūra	Jūra	Jura/Jura_Gals
Jūra	Jūra	Jura/Jura_Taurage
Jūra	Šešuvis	Jura/Sesupe_Skirgalai
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	194	Lielupe_MI/194
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	198	Lielupe_MI/198
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	213	Lielupe_MI/213
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	220	Lielupe_MI/220
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Alėja	Lielupe_MI/Aleja
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Audruvė	Lielupe_MI/Audruve
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Beržtalis	Lielupe_MI/Berstalis
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Kivė	Lielupe_MI/Kive
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Leparė	Lielupe_MI/Lepare
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Oglainė	Lielupe_MI/Oglaine
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Platonė	Lielupe_MI/Platone
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Plonyte	Lielupe_MI/Plonyte
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Šešėvė	Lielupe_MI/Seseve
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Sidabra	Lielupe_MI/Sidarba
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Švėtė	Lielupe_MI/Svete
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Švėtelė	Lielupe_MI/Svetele
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Svirkalnis	Lielupe_MI/Svirkalnis
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Švitinys	Lielupe_MI/Svitinys
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Vilkija	Lielupe_MI/Vilikija1
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Virčiuvis	Lielupe_MI/Virciuvis
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Viršytis	Lielupe_MI/Virsytis
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Yslykis	Lielupe_MI/Ylksys

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Merkys	Merkys	Merkys/Merkys
Merkys	Ūla – Pelesa	Merkys/Pelesa
Merkys	Šalčia	Merkys/Salčia
Merkys	Varėnė	Merkys/Varene
Merkys	Verseka	Merkys/Verseka
Minija	Minija	Minija/Minija_Kartena
Minija	Minija	Minija/Minija_zem_kartenas
Minija	Veiviržas	Minija/Veivirzas
Minija	Žvelsa	Minija/Zvelsa
Mūša	Daugyvenė	Musa/Daugyvene
Mūša	Kruoja	Musa/Kruoja
Mūša	Kulpė	Musa/Kulpe
Mūša	Lėvuo	Musa/Levuo
Mūša	Mažupė	Musa/Mazupe
Mūša	Mūša	Musa/Musa_kopa
Mūša	Pyvesa	Musa/Pyvesa
Mūša	Šiladis	Musa/Siladys
Mūša	Tatula	Musa/Tatula
Nemunas	Baltoji Ančia	Nemunas/Baltoji
Nemunas	Gėgė	Nemunas/Gege
Nemunas	Jiesia	Nemunas/Jiesiai
Nemunas	Miltuva	Nemunas/Miltuva
Nemunas	Nemunas	Nemunas/Nemunas
Nemunas	Peršėkė	Nemunas/Perseke
Nemunas	Strėva	Nemunas/Streva
Nemunas	Strėva	Nemunas/Streva_ecl_semeliskes
Nemunas	Šyša	Nemunas/Sysa_Silute
Nemunas	Verknė	Nemunas/Verkne_Vebyksles
Nemunėlis	Apaščia	Nemunelis/Apasciai
Nemunėlis	Nemunėlis	Nemunelis/Nemunelis_LT
Neris	Musė	Neris/Muse
Neris	Neris	Neris/Neris_upe
Neris	Vilnia	Neris/Vilnia
Neris	Vokė	Neris/Voke
Nevėžis	Aluona	Nevezis/Aluona
Nevėžis	Barupė	Nevezis/Barupe
Nevėžis	Kiršinas	Nevezis/Kirstina
Nevėžis	Nevėžis	Nevezis/Nevezis
Nevėžis	Obelis	Nevezis/Obelis
Nevėžis	Nevėžis	Nevezis/Panevezis
Nevėžis	Smilga	Nevezis/Smilga
Nevėžis	Šušvė	Nevezis/Susve
Nevėžis	Upytė	Nevezis/Upyte
Pajūrio upės	1127	Parejais/1127
Pajūrio upės	1129	Parejais/1129
Pajūrio upės	1131	Parejais/1131
Pajūrio upės	1158	Parejais/1158

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Pajūrio upės	No name	Parejais/Kretinga
Pajūrio upės	No name	Parejais/Kursu_Kapa
Pajūrio upės	No name	Parejais/Kursu_laguna1
Pajūrio upės	No name	Parejais/Kursu_laguna2
Pajūrio upės	No name	Parejais/Kursu_laguna3
Pajūrio upės	No name	Parejais/Kursu_laguna4
Pajūrio upės	No name	Parejais/Kursu_laguna5
Pajūrio upės	Ošupis	Parejais/Osupis2
Pajūrio upės	Akmėna	Parejais/Pareja_Akmėne
Pajūrio upės	Smeltalė	Parejais/Smeltale
Prieglius	Prieglius	Prieglius/Prieglius
Šešupė	Jotija	Sesupe/Jotijaa
Šešupė	Nova	Sesupe/Nova
Šešupė	Pilvė	Sesupe/Pilve
Šešupė	Šešupė	Sesupe/Sesupe
Šešupė	Šešupė	Sesupe/Sesupe_upst
Šešupė	Širvinta	Sesupe/Sirvinta
Šešupė	Višakis	Sesupe/Viskakis1
Šventoji	Jara	Shventoji/Jara
Šventoji	Šventoji	Shventoji/Shventoji_A
Šventoji	Šventoji	Shventoji/Shventoji_K
Šventoji	Siesartis	Shventoji/Siesartis
Šventoji	Širvinta	Shventoji/Sirvinta
Šventoji	Suraiža-Virinta	Shventoji/Suraiza
Šventoji	Vyžuona	Shventoji/Vyžuona
Šventoji	Šventoji	Sveentoji/Sventoji
Šventoji	Šventoji	Sveentoji/Sventoji_Klaip
Venta	222	Venta/222
Venta	223	Venta/223
Venta	Dabikinė	Venta/Dabikina
Venta	Uogys	Venta/Uogys
Venta	Vadakstis	Venta/Vadakstis
Venta	Varduva	Venta/Varduva
Venta	Venta	Venta/Venta
Venta	Virvyčia	Venta/Virvyčia
Žeimėna	Dumblė-Kiauna	Zeimėna/Dumble1
Žeimėna	Žeimėna	Zeimėna/Kaltėna
Žeimėna	Lakaja	Zeimėna/Lakaja
Žeimėna	Stirnelė	Zeimėna/Stirnele
Žeimėna	Žeimėna	Zeimėna/Zeimėna

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Table 2. The values of the calibration parameters for 19 regions.

Table	Coefficient	Bartuva	Dauguva	Dubysa	Jura	Lielupe_MI	Merkys
BSN	CDN	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02
BSN	CMN	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001
BSN	DEPIMP_BSN	0	0	0	0	0	3000
BSN	NPERCO	0,134	0,134	0,134	0,134	0,134	0,134
BSN	RSDCO	0,035	0,035	0,035	0,035	0,035	0,035
BSN	SDNCO	0,9	0,9	0,9	0,9	1,05	0,9
BSN	SFTMP	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5
BSN	SMFMN	4,5	4,5	4,5	4,5	4,5	3
BSN	SMFMX	4,5	4,5	4,5	4,5	4,5	3
BSN	SMTMP	1	1	1	1	1	2
BSN	SPCON	0,00002	0,00004	0,0001	0,0004	0,00001	0,0001
BSN	SPEXP	2	1	1	1	3	1
BSN	SURLAG	0,32	0,32	0,32	0,32	0,32	0,32
BSN	TIMP	1	1	1	1	1	0,1
GW	ALPHA_BF	0,08	0,07	0,06	0,05	0,1	0,005
GW	GW_DELAY	0,3	0,3	2	0,3	0,3	60
GW	GW_REVAP	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,12
GW	GWQMN	100	100	100	100	100	100
GW	HLIFE_NGW	20	25	30	20	50	15
GW	RCHRG_DP	0,01	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05
GW	REVAPMN	125	125	125	150	125	125
HRU	CANMX	5	10	10	15	10	10
HRU	ESCO	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01
HRU	LAT_TTIME	0	0	0	0	0	3
HRU	OV_N	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14
MGT	CN2	-24%	-15%	-15%	-15%	-15%	-15%
RTE	CH_COV	1	1	1	1	1	1
RTE	CH_EROD	0	0	0	0	0	0
RTE	CH_N2	0,06	0,06	0,06	0,06	0,06	0,06
SOL	SOL_AWC1	-5%	-9%	30%	30%	44%	30%
SOL	SOL_AWC2	-5%	-9%	30%	30%	44%	30%
SOL	SOL_K1	500%	500%	500%	500%	462%	500%
SOL	SOL_K2	500%	500%	500%	500%	462%	500%
SOL	USLE_K1	-50%	-96%	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%
SOL	USLE_K2	-50%	-96%	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%
SWQ	BC1	0,55	0,55	0,55	0,55	0,55	0,55
SWQ	BC2	1,1	1,1	1,1	1,1	1,1	1,1
SWQ	BC3	0,21	0,21	0,21	0,21	0,21	0,21
SWQ	BC4	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2
SWQ	RK1	0,01	0,01	0,25	0,15	0,25	0,25
SWQ	RK2	2,5	2,5	2,5	0,5	1,5	2,5
SWQ	RK3	0,15	0,01	0,25	0,25	0,12	0,25
SWQ	RS1	1	1	1	1	1	1

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SWQ	RS2	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001
SWQ	RS3	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01
SWQ	RS4	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05
SWQ	RS5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5

Table 2 (continued). The values of the calibration parameters which differ from the default ELLE&PAIC(2012a) for 19 regions.

Table	Coefficient	Minija	Musa	Nemunas	Nemunelis	Neris	Nevezis	Parejais
BSN	CDN	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02
BSN	CMN	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001
BSN	DEPIMP_BSN	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
BSN	NPERCO	0,134	0,134	0,134	0,134	0,134	0,134	0,134
BSN	RSDCO	0,035	0,035	0,035	0,035	0,035	0,035	0,035
BSN	SDNCO	0,9	1	0,9	0,9	0,9	0,95	0,9
BSN	SFTMP	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5
BSN	SMFMN	4,5	4,5	4,5	4,5	3	4,5	4,5
BSN	SMFMX	4,5	4,5	4,5	4,5	3	4,5	4,5
BSN	SMTMP	1	1	1	1	1,4	1	1
BSN	SPCON	0,0001	0,0001	0,0001	0,0001	0,0001	0,0001	0,0001
BSN	SPEXP	2	2,5	1	1	1	1	1
BSN	SURLAG	0,5	0,32	0,32	0,32	0,32	0,32	0,32
BSN	TIMP	1	1	1	1	0,1	1	1
GW	ALPHA_BF	0,2	0,07	0,07	0,07	0,05	0,07	0,07
GW	GW_DELAY	0,3	0,3	0,3	0,3	10	0,3	0,3
GW	GW_REVAP	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02
GW	GWQMN	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
GW	HLIFE_NGW	20	30	25	50	18	40	35
GW	RCHRG_DP	0,05	0	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,09	0,05
GW	REVAPMN	125	125	125	125	125	125	125
HRU	CANMX	15	10	10	10	10	15	10
HRU	ESCO	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01
HRU	LAT_TTIME	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
HRU	OV_N	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14
MGT	CN2	-25%	-24%	-15%	-15%	-15%	-19%	-15%
RTE	CH_COV	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
RTE	CH_EROD	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
RTE	CH_N2	0,06	0,06	0,06	0,06	0,06	0,06	0,06
SOL	SOL_AWC1	56%	0%	30%	30%	30%	27%	30%
SOL	SOL_AWC2	56%	0%	30%	30%	30%	27%	30%
SOL	SOL_K1	500%	500%	500%	500%	500%	500%	500%
SOL	SOL_K2	500%	500%	500%	500%	500%	500%	500%
SOL	USLE_K1	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%
SOL	USLE_K2	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%
SWQ	BC1	0,55	0,55	0,55	0,55	0,55	0,55	0,55
SWQ	BC2	1,1	1,1	1,1	1,1	1,1	1,1	1,1

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SWQ	BC3	0,21	0,21	0,21	0,21	0,21	0,21	0,21
SWQ	BC4	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,23
SWQ	RK1	0,03	0,25	0,25	0,25	0,25	0,25	0,25
SWQ	RK2	2,5	0,5	2,5	2,5	2,5	2,5	2,5
SWQ	RK3	0,03	0,2	0,25	0,25	0,25	0,25	0,25
SWQ	RS1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
SWQ	RS2	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001
SWQ	RS3	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01
SWQ	RS4	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05
SWQ	RS5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,05

Table 2 (continued). The values of the calibration parameters which differ from the default ELLE&PAIC(2012a) for 19 regions.

Table	Coefficient	Prieglius	Sesupe	Shventoji	Sveentoji	Venta	Zeimena
BSN	CDN	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02
BSN	CMN	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001
BSN	DEPIMP_BSN	0	0	0	0	0	8000
BSN	NPERCO	0,134	0,134	0,134	0,134	0,134	0,134
BSN	RSDCO	0,035	0,035	0,035	0,035	0,035	0,035
BSN	SDNCO	0,9	0,9	0,9	0,9	0,9	0,9
BSN	SFTMP	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5
BSN	SMFMN	4,5	4,5	4,5	3	4,5	3
BSN	SMFMX	4,5	4,5	4,5	3	4,5	3
BSN	SMTMP	1	1	1	1,5	1	2
BSN	SPCON	0,0001	0,0001	0,0001	0,0001	0,0001	0,0001
BSN	SPEXP	1	1	2	1	1	1
BSN	SURLAG	0,32	0,32	0,32	0,32	0,32	0,32
BSN	TIMP	1	1	1	0,1	1	0,1
GW	ALPHA_BF	0,07	0,07	0,04	0,06	0,07	0,03
GW	GW_DELAY	0,3	0,3	0,3	0,3	0,3	30
GW	GW_REVAP	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,12
GW	GWQMN	100	100	100	100	100	100
GW	HLIFE_NGW	20	30	50	25	25	10
GW	RCHRG_DP	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,35
GW	REVAPMN	125	125	125	125	125	125
HRU	CANMX	10	10	20	10	10	10
HRU	ESCO	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01
HRU	LAT_TTIME	0	0	0	0	0	3
HRU	OV_N	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14
MGT	CN2	-15%	-15%	-30%	-15%	-15%	-15%
RTE	CH_COV	1	1	1	1	1	1
RTE	CH_EROD	0	0	0	0	0	0
RTE	CH_N2	0,06	0,06	0,06	0,06	0,06	0,06
SOL	SOL_AWC1	30%	30%	57%	30%	30%	30%
SOL	SOL_AWC2	30%	30%	57%	30%	30%	30%

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SOL	SOL_K1	500%	500%	500%	500%	500%	500%
SOL	SOL_K2	500%	500%	500%	500%	500%	500%
SOL	USLE_K1	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%
SOL	USLE_K2	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%
SWQ	BC1	0,55	0,55	0,55	0,55	0,55	0,55
SWQ	BC2	1,1	1,1	1,1	1,1	1,1	1,1
SWQ	BC3	0,21	0,21	0,21	0,21	0,21	0,21
SWQ	BC4	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2
SWQ	RK1	0,25	0,25	0,25	0,25	0,25	0,25
SWQ	RK2	2,5	2,5	2,5	2,5	2,5	2,5
SWQ	RK3	0,25	0,25	0,25	0,25	0,25	0,25
SWQ	RS1	1	1	1	1	1	1
SWQ	RS2	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001
SWQ	RS3	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01
SWQ	RS4	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05
SWQ	RS5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5

Table 3. Calibration results (NSE and PBIAS) for Nemunas-Smalininkai.

Variable	Calibration 2000-2005		Validation 2006-2010	
	NSE	PBIAS	NSE	PBIAS
Q	0.74	7%	0.75	6%
N-NO3	0.71	6%	0.75	27%
P-PO4	0.32	-20%	-0.03	-32%

Fig. 1. Observed (red) and modeled (green) discharge. Nemunas at Smalininkai.

Fig. 2. Observed (red) and modeled (green) N-NO₃ load. Nemunas at Smalininkai.

Fig. 3. Observed (red) and modeled (green) N-NH₄ load. Nemunas at Smalininkai.

Fig. 4. Observed (red) and modeled (green) Norg load. Nemunas at Smalininkai.

Fig. 5. Observed (red) and modeled (green) P-PO4 load. Nemunas at Smalininkai.

Fig. 6. Observed (red) and modeled (green) Porg load. Nemunas at Smalininkai.

2.2.2. Methodology for nutrient source separation

The cornerstone of the methodology for separation of the sources of the nutrients entering the Lithuanian surface waters is the ability of SWAT modelling system to calculate the outflow of nutrients from every HRU (hydrological response unit).

The methodology includes the following steps:

1. Calculation by the water quality modelling system for the selected time period specifying the output of the nutrient loads to the reaches from each individual HRU. Note that due to large output file size the output time step should be set as large as possible (e.g. 1 Year when calculating 11-year period in Section 2.2.3).
2. Summing up the nutrient loads from the HRUs of the same land use (agricultural, pastures, forest, urban and water, see Table 9 in ELLE & PAIC (2012a)) with selected spatial (in our case – subbasin) and temporal (in our case – yearly) aggregation.
3. Calculation of the loads from the separated sources according to the following scheme:
 - a. **Transboundary sources** – loads entering Lithuanian surface waters as (1) the inputs to the upper reaches crossing the border of Lithuania and (2) diffuse sources from non-Lithuanian parts of catchments of boundary rivers. The transboundary pollution is not separated according to its origin.
 - b. **Background sources** – nutrient loads to reaches from HRUs of land use “forest” and “water”.

- c. **Diffuse agricultural sources** (or non-point sources) – nutrient loads to reaches from HRUs of land use “agricultural” and “pastures”.
 - d. **Other anthropogenic sources** – nutrient loads to reaches from the point sources and from the HRUs of land use “urban”.
 - i. **Stormwater loads** are a part of load entering surface water from the land use type “urban”.
 - ii. **Point source loads** are the loads from point sources. Loads from **municipal waste water treatment plants** and **industrial plants** may be separated in this step.
4. The calculated loads are recalculated per area of subbasin and per time unit (year).

The proposed methodology of the nutrient source separation is along with the guideline EuroHARP (2007a).

The methodology is realised in PAIC SWAT software. The functionality of the PAIC SWAT will be described in the software user manual in Stage III.

The Technical specifications require calculation for loads other than listed above:

1. **Atmospheric loads.** In SWAT atmospheric loads enter particular HRU and appear as a part of loads from that HRU. The non-linear processes within HRU do not allow to separate the share of atmospheric load within the total load from the elementary catchment. The principal possibility for separation of these loads is a modification of setups by removal of particular source and calculation of the load difference at the reference situation and the modified situation. However under such an approach the sum of all loads (unsewered inhabitants, background, agricultural, atmospheric, background etc) will differ from the total load accounting all sources due to non-linearity of the system. Therefore atmospheric loads calculated in Section 2.2.3 should be regarded separately.
2. **Loads from settlements not connected to sewage treatment facilities.** The sum of loads from unsewered inhabitants is provided in Section 2.2.3 by River basin district.
3. **Settlements connected to sewage treatment facilities and industrial plants.** These classes of point sources can not be separated from the other point sources due to the point source database does not distinguish the type of point source. EPA provided a list of **municipal waste water treatment plants**. We regarded the rest of point sources as pollution from the **industrial plants** in Section 2.2.3.

We have to note that SWAT software has an auxiliary feature – **load of algae from the catchments (HRUs) via the surface run-off**. This load of organic nutrients is calculated internally and can be neither calibrated (via user defined parameters) nor separated (via output of calculation results). Thus, the nutrient load to surface water bodies by algae load “escapes” the direct accounting.

The attempt to investigate undocumented structure of SWAT output files allowed the estimation of this algae load. SWAT output files contain parameters *chlain* and *chlaout* for each subbasin. These parameters stand for Chlorophyll-a load entering the river stretch of particular subbasin and leaving the subbasin, respectively. We assume that

$$\text{“load of Chl-a to the surface water (river stretch)”}^{(i)} = \text{chlain}^{(i)} - \text{chlaout}^{(i-1)}$$

Here (i) denotes the subbasin in the hierarchical chain of subbasins. For upstream subbasin $chain^{(0)}$ equals to 0.

The load of organic nitrogen and phosphorus by algae can further be recalculated from Chl-a using the default SWAT values for algal N/P content. The respective formula are

$$N_{algae} = Chl-a * WWQ.AI1 / WWQ.AI0 * 1000$$

$$P_{algae} = Chl-a * WWQ.AI2 / WWQ.AI0 * 1000$$

Here,

- N_{algae} is algae N load, P_{algae} is algae P load, $Chl-a$ is chlorophyll-A load,
- $WWQ.AI0$ is SWAT coefficient from WWQ file – „ratio of chlorophyll-a to algal biomass (microgram-chla/mg algae)”,
- $WWQ.AI1$ is SWAT coefficient from WWQ file – „fraction of algal biomass that is nitrogen (mg N/mg algae)”, and
- $WWQ.AI2$ is SWAT coefficient from WWQ file – „fraction of algal biomass that is phosphorus (mg P/mg algae)”

Note that the load of nutrients via algae can not be distinguished at the level of particular HRUs and thus separated as load from different land use type. We refer to this load as “algae nutrient load” throughout the report.

2.2.3. Calculation of yearly nutrient loads to surface water bodies

The methodology of Section 2.2.2 was applied for the calculation of the loads from the international, background, diffuse agricultural, urban stormwater, other anthropogenic and algae sources (6 source classes) to the surface water bodies (river reaches) of Lithuania. Calculation was performed for time period 2000-2010. The following outputs were prepared:

1. The spatial distribution (spatial resolution – subbasin of modelling system) of mean annual loads separating different pollution sources. The respective maps for main three sources (agricultural, background and anthropogenic) and total of all six source classes of N-NO₃, N_{tot}, P-PO₄ and P_{tot} loads are shown in Figs 7-22. The loads from the respective source per total area of the catchment are given in these Figures.
2. The summary of the mean annual load (in tons per year) to each of 4 Lithuanian river basin districts, for each of the 4 main nutrients and for each of the pollution sources is given in Table 4.
3. The electronic deliverable is prepared:
 - a. File basin.zip contains zipped ArcMap shapefile of subbasins.
 - b. File loads.xlsx is an Excel file containing loads of particular nutrients (columns NO₃, N_{tot}, PO₄ and P_{tot}) from particular sources and total (suffixes of column names _AGRC, _BCKG, _STMW, _TRSB, _POSR, _ALGA and _TOT correspond to agricultural, background, urban stormwater, transboundary, point sources, algae sources and total of all sources) for all subbasins.

- c. The load table can be used with ArcMap joining cach_id attribute of subbasin shapes with Excel column “cachid”.

Table 4. Mean annual nutrient loads from various sources to Lithuanian River basin districts for time period 2000-2010. Point source is divided as waste water treatment plants (WWTP) and industrial plants (IP).

RBD	Nutrient	Loads, t/year						Total
		Agricult.	Background	Stormw.	PointSource (WWTP/IP)	Transb.	Algae	
Nemunas	NO3	17582	3995	2	639 (492/147)	9792	0	32010
Venta	NO3	2909	599	0	111 (22/89)	167	0	3785
Lielupe	NO3	4324	1837	0	54 (50/4)	37	0	6251
Dauguva	NO3	473	219	0	260 (13/247)	9	0	961
Nemunas	Ntot	25906	4117	2	2036 (1672/364)	18581	85956	136598
Venta	Ntot	4252	611	0	197 (63/134)	777	13582	19419
Lielupe	Ntot	5768	1868	0	291 (260/31)	228	21359	29514
Dauguva	Ntot	554	221	0	1440 (18/1422)	87	2758	5060
Nemunas	PO4	540	34	0	148 (125/23)	362	0	1084
Venta	PO4	81	5	0	29 (11/18)	4	0	118
Lielupe	PO4	93	6	0	18 (14/4)	1	0	118
Dauguva	PO4	8	2	0	100 (6/94)	0	0	110
Nemunas	Ptot	1572	52	0	249 (213/36)	1130	16117	19120
Venta	Ptot	247	7	0	35 (16/19)	115	2547	2949
Lielupe	Ptot	273	9	0	25 (18/7)	36	4005	4348
Dauguva	Ptot	18	3	0	139 (7/132)	15	517	691

Analysing the calculation results one have to consider that the distribution of loads reflect not only the input of various substances into the system but also transformation and retention processes in the catchments which depend on land use, soil type, agricultural praxis, hydrological regime etc.

The distinct spatial pattern of nutrient load density can be seen despite the fact that there is a high variability of the loads between neighbouring subbasins. The higher loads in western and northeastern part of country are related to higher runoff modulus. The load variation in the central part of country is highly dependent on the fraction of agricultural land in subbasins. There is a distinct minimum of loads along the south-east border, associated with the soil type and land use. The higher loads (especially for P) are remarkable near the urban agglomerations of Vilnius and Kaunas.

The results may be indirectly compared with EPA (2010a, b) taking into account that in these documents agricultural loads are calculated as the loads applied to catchment (in contrary to this report where the loads to surface water bodies are modelled). The spatial pattern of the loads is rather similar though except that RBD reports indicate very high loads in the subbasins of high agricultural activity.

The spatial distribution of the number of **unsewered inhabitants** is given by EPA. We assume the annual loads from unsewered inhabitants according to NIVA (2000) and EWPCA (1997). We used values given for Sweden (60 kg BOD7, 12 kg Ntot, 2,5 kg Ptot). The mean annual loads from unsewered inhabitants are summarised by river basin district and nutrient

in Table 5.

Fig. 7. Distribution of N-NO₃ loads from agriculture, kg/ha/year. 2000-2010.

Fig. 8. Distribution of N_{tot} loads from agriculture, kg/ha/year. 2000-2010.

Fig. 9. Distribution of N-NO₃ background loads, kg/ha/year. 2000-2010.

Fig. 10. Distribution of N_{tot} background loads, kg/ha/year. 2000-2010.

Fig. 11. Distribution of N-NO3 anthropogenic loads, kg/ha/year. 2000-2010.

Fig. 12. Distribution of Ntot anthropogenic loads, kg/ha/year. 2000-2010.

Fig. 13. Distribution of total N-NO₃ loads, kg/ha/year. 2000-2010.

Fig. 14. Distribution of total N_{tot} loads, kg/ha/year. 2000-2010.

Fig. 15. Distribution of P-PO4 agricultural loads, kg/ha/year. 2000-2010.

Fig. 16. Distribution of Ptot agricultural loads, kg/ha/year. 2000-2010.

Fig. 17. Distribution of P-PO₄ background loads, kg/ha/year. 2000-2010.

Fig. 18. Distribution of P_{tot} background loads, kg/ha/year. 2000-2010.

Fig. 19. Distribution of P-PO4 anthropogenic loads, kg/ha/year. 2000-2010.

Fig. 20. Distribution of Ptot anthropogenic loads, kg/ha/year. 2000-2010.

Fig. 21. Distribution of total P-PO4 loads, kg/ha/year. 2000-2010.

Fig. 22. Distribution of total Ptot loads, kg/ha/year. 2000-2010.

The Technical specifications require separation of **atmospheric loads**. The principal possibility for separation of these loads is a modification of setups by removal of atmospheric source and calculation of the load difference at the reference situation and the modified situation. However, under such an approach the sum of all loads (background, agricultural, atmospheric, background etc) will differ from the total load accounting all sources due to non-linearity of the system. The mean annual atmospheric loads calculated

as a difference between the reference set-ups and the modified setups (no atmospheric N input) are summarised by river basin district and nutrient in Table 6.

This Table 6 illustrates a non-linearity of the system. Although real atmospheric load of phosphorus is zero, the switching off of atmosphere nitrogen loads results in the increase of the phosphorus loads into the surface water bodies (decrease of N load leads to lower plant biomass and, subsequently – higher P washout from the soil).

Table 5. Mean annual N and P loads from unsewered inhabitants for time period 2000-2010.

	Ntot, t/yr	Ptot, t/yr
Nemunas RBD	1438	300
Dauguva RBD	25	5
Lielupe RBD	273	57
Venta RBD	181	38

Table 6. Mean annual atmospheric N and P loads for time period 2000-2010

	Ntot, t/yr	Ptot, t/yr
Nemunas RBD	2984	-145
Dauguva RBD	451	-35
Lielupe RBD	258	-85
Venta RBD	144	5

2.2.4. Nutrient retention

The EuroHARP (2007a, b) treats the retention of the nutrient loads in the catchment as the retention of the loads entered into surface water system. Therefore we considered the retention of nutrients as the difference between the nutrient input in the system and the nutrient output from the system.

The nutrient input in the system is the sum of all loads, calculated in Section 2.2.3 according to methodics described in Section 2.2.2. The nutrient output is the time integral of water discharge multiplied by nutrient concentration at the lowest reaches of the catchment, i.e. rivers either entering the sea or flowing out from the territory of Lithuania.

Table 7. Mean annual nutrient retention in the river system of the Lithuanian River basin districts for time period 2000-2010.

River basin district	Nutrient	Retention, t/year	Retention, %
Nemunas	Ntot	89001	65%
Venta	Ntot	13746	71%
Lielupe	Ntot	21084	71%
Dauguva	Ntot	3874	77%
Nemunas	Ptot	18074	95%
Venta	Ptot	2760	94%
Lielupe	Ptot	4076	94%
Dauguva	Ptot	628	91%

The summary of the mean annual retention (both in tons per year and in % of the loads from

catchments) for each of 4 Lithuanian river basin districts, for total nitrogen and phosphorus is given in Table 7. The maps of the retention of the total N and P in the rivers (tons per kilometre of river length and per year) are presented in Figs. 23 – 24, respectively.

Fig. 23. Distribution of N_{tot} retention (t/km/year) in river system of Lithuania, 2000-2010.

Fig. 24. Distribution of P_{tot} retention (t/km/year) in river system of Lithuania, 2000-2010.

The percentage of nitrogen retention is between 65% and 77%, it is higher in smaller basins. The retention of phosphorus is higher (91% to 95%) as that of nitrogen, it is associated with settling of P-adsorbing particles. Thus, relative phosphorus retention is higher in larger RBD's, and the effect of reservoirs is evident (Fig. 24).

Let us consider the specific requirements of the technical specifications which cannot be directly accounted for due to specifics of SWAT modelling system):

1. **Retention in buffer zones.** Contrary to the conceptual models SWAT does not distinguish the loads from the catchments into the buffer zones. The elementary spatial element of the modelling system is HRU, and it is related to the combination of land use / soil type. Further, the retention in buffer zones occurs within the catchment processes, i.e. it is already included in calculating the loads from the catchment. In the same time we may estimate the retention in the buffer zones by calculation of the additional case applying 15 m wide buffer zones along all rivers. Then the retention in the buffer zones can be evaluated as a difference between the loads to the surface bodies in the reference setups and in the modified setups. A summary of the retention in the buffer zones calculated by such a method is provided in Table 8. Table contains both absolute mean retention values (t/y) and percentage of the load to the surface water bodies retented in the buffers zones. One may consider that
 - a. The retention is higher for the inorganic nutrients due to the organic loads (algae) bypasses the buffer zones in SWAT.
 - b. The retention is higher for phosphates in comparison with nitrates.
 - c. The buffer zones has higher influence in the agricultural areas.

Table 8. Mean annual nutrient retention in the buffer zones of the river system of the Lithuanian River basin districts for time period 2000-2010.

River basin district	Nutrient	Retention, t/year	Retention, %
Nemunas	NO3	8766	27,38%
Venta	NO3	1475	38,96%
Lielupe	NO3	2224	35,59%
Dauguva	NO3	263	27,34%
Nemunas	Ntot	15047	11,02%
Venta	Ntot	2453	12,63%
Lielupe	Ntot	2968	10,06%
Dauguva	Ntot	347	6,86%
Nemunas	PO4	479	44,20%
Venta	PO4	72	61,33%
Lielupe	PO4	82	69,28%
Dauguva	PO4	8	6,86%
Nemunas	Ptot	1212	6,34%
Venta	Ptot	183	6,21%
Lielupe	Ptot	144	3,31%
Dauguva	Ptot	20	2,83%

2. **Retention in wetlands.** The SWAT algorithm of accounting for wetlands transfers part of the loads from every HRU of given subbasin through the wetlands. This part equals to the wetland percentage in the subbasin. The retention in the wetlands is accounted in SWAT but no mass balance components can be acquired – the load from every HRU already is decreased by the retention in wetlands and is not reported separately. Further, the retention in wetlands occurs within the catchment processes, i.e. is already included in calculating the loads from the catchment in the surface water bodies. In the same time we may estimate the retention in the wetlands by

calculation of the additional case without the wetlands, i.e. setting to zero the wetland parameters WET_FR (fraction of subbasin area that drains into wetlands), WET_NSA (surface area of wetlands at normal water level), WET_NVOL (volume of water stored in wetlands when filled to normal water level), WET_MXSA (surface area of wetlands at maximum water level), WET_MXVOL (volume of water stored in wetlands when filled to maximum water level) and WET_VOL (initial volume of water in wetlands). Then the retention in the wetlands can be evaluated as a difference between the loads to the surface water bodies in the modified setups and the reference setups. A summary of the retention in the wetlands calculated by such a method is provided in Table 9. Table contains both absolute mean retention values (t/y) and percentage of the load to the surface water bodies retented in the wetlands.

Table 9. Mean annual nutrient retention in the wetlands of the Lithuanian River basin districts for time period 2000-2010.

River basin district	Nutrient	Retention, t/year	Retention, %
Nemunas	NO3	450.01	1.4%
Venta	NO3	17.71	0.5%
Lielupe	NO3	304.65	4.9%
Dauguva	NO3	2.87	0.3%
Nemunas	Ntot	486.95	0.4%
Venta	Ntot	24.47	0.1%
Lielupe	Ntot	317.23	1.1%
Dauguva	Ntot	3.15	0.1%
Nemunas	PO4	4.69	0.4%
Venta	PO4	0.44	0.4%
Lielupe	PO4	1.72	1.5%
Dauguva	PO4	0.04	0.0%
Nemunas	Ptot	9.60	0.1%
Venta	Ptot	1.29	0.0%
Lielupe	Ptot	3.26	0.1%
Dauguva	Ptot	0.07	0.0%

- Retention in lakes and ponds.** The error in SWAT model related to lake modelling was identified. Namely, the precipitation over the lakes is accounted twice – once as precipitation over the HRU of land use type “water” and then as the precipitation over the specified lake area. This results in excess of water, especially for subbasins with high share of lakes. To avoid the problem lake processes are not modelled in the reference set-ups, accounting lakes only as HRUs with land use “water”. In the same time we may estimate the retention in the lakes and ponds by calculation of the additional case with enabled lake processes. This case leads to increased runoff, however the retention in the lakes and ponds can be evaluated as a difference between the loads to the surface water bodies in the reference setups and the modified setups. A summary of the retention in the lakes and ponds calculated by such a method is provided in Table 10. Table contains both absolute mean retention values (t/y) and percentage of the load to the surface water bodies retented in the lakes and ponds.

Table 10. Mean annual nutrient retention in the lakes and ponds of the river system of the Lithuanian River basin districts for time period 2000-2010.

River basin district	Nutrient	Retention, t/year	Retention, %
Nemunas	NO3	882.9	2.76%
Venta	NO3	26.1	0.69%
Lielupe	NO3	36.4	0.58%
Dauguva	NO3	134.0	13.95%
Nemunas	Ntot	1295.7	0.95%
Venta	Ntot	40.8	0.21%
Lielupe	Ntot	43.0	0.15%
Dauguva	Ntot	149.6	2.96%
Nemunas	PO4	29.9	2.76%
Venta	PO4	0.8	0.67%
Lielupe	PO4	0.5	0.40%
Dauguva	PO4	1.7	1.50%
Nemunas	Ptot	84.4	0.44%
Venta	Ptot	2.7	0.09%
Lielupe	Ptot	1.3	0.03%
Dauguva	Ptot	3.6	0.53%

2.2.5. Methodology for calculating source apportionment

The cornerstones of the methodology for the source apportionment for the riverine loads entering the Baltic Sea are (1) the methodology of separation of the sources of the nutrients entering the Lithuanian surface waters developed in Section 2.2.2 and (2) the ability of SWAT modelling system to calculate the riverine outflow of nutrients from every subbasin.

The methodology includes the following steps:

1. Calculation by the water quality modelling system for the selected time period and calculation of the separated nutrient (N-NO₃, N-tot, P-PO₄, P-tot) loads from the considered sources (transboundary, background, diffuse agricultural, stormwater, point source and algae) for each subbasin of the modelling system according to the methodics in Section 2.2.2.
2. Building of the nutrient mass balance according to EuroHARP (2007a) for each nutrient and each subbasin as

$$L_{in} + L_{catchment} - R = L_{out}$$

Here L_{in} is riverine nutrient load into the subbasin (transboundary pollution if the river enters Lithuania or zero at the very upstream subbasin or load from the upstream catchment otherwise), $L_{catchment}$ is the nutrient load from the catchment of the subbasin calculated in p.1, R is the retention in the river stream calculated by SWAT, and L_{out} is the riverine nutrient load flowing out of the subbasin (entering Baltic Sea, leaving Lithuania or otherwise flowing into downstream subbasin).

3. The retention rate (%) is calculated for each nutrient and each subbasin as

$$R\% = L_{out} / (L_{in} + L_{catchment})$$

4. The separation of the nutrient sources is performed for each nutrient in each of the subbasins under assumption that retention rate is the same for the same nutrients regardless of their source. Assuming that the source separation is available at the inflow L_{in} we calculated source-separated loads at the outflow for i-th ($i=1,2,\dots,6$) source as

$$L_{out,i} = R\% * (L_{in,i} + L_{catchment,i})$$

5. Propagating of algorithm of pp.(2-4) through the river (or hierarchical subbasin) network produces the source apportionment of the riverine outflowing loads from each subbasins – ultimately for riverine loads entering the Baltic Sea or leaving Lithuania.
6. The calculated loads are recalculated as tons per year for each subbasin for each nutrient and each pollution source.

The proposed methodology of the source apportionment of the riverine nutrient loads is realised in PAIC SWAT software. The functionality of the PAIC SWAT will be described in the software user manual in Stage III.

2.2.6. Calculation of riverine nutrient load apportionment

The methodology of Section 2.2.5 was applied for the calculation of the apportionment of the riverine loads from international, background, diffuse agricultural, urban stormwater, anthropogenic point source and algae sources (6 source classes) in the river stretches of Lithuania. Calculation was performed for time period 2000-2010. The following outputs were prepared:

1. The spatial distribution (spatial resolution – river stretch in the subbasin of modelling system) of mean annual riverine loads separating different pollution sources. The respective maps for total riverine loads of four nutrients (N-NO₃, N_{tot}, P-PO₄ and P_{tot} loads) are shown in Figs 25-28.
2. The summary of the mean annual riverine loads (in tons per year) entering Baltic Sea or leaving territory of Lithuania from each of 4 Lithuanian river basin districts, for each of the 4 main nutrients and for each of the 6 main pollution sources is given in Table 11.
3. The electronic deliverable is prepared:
 - File basin.zip contains zipped ArcMap shapefile of subbasins.
 - File reach.xlsx is an Excel file containing riverine loads of particular nutrients (columns NO₃, N_{tot}, PO₄ and P_{tot}) from particular sources and total (suffixes of column names _AGRC, _BCKG, _STMW, _TRSB, _POSR, _ALGA and _TOT correspond to agricultural, background, urban stormwater, transboundary, point sources, algae sources and total of all sources) for all subbasins.
 - The riverine load table can be used with ArcMap joining cach_id attribute of subbasin shapes with Excel column “cachid”.

Table 11. Mean annual riverine nutrient loads with source apportionment from Lithuanian River basin districts for time period 2000-2010.

RBD	Nutrient	Loads, t/year						Total
		Agricult.	Background	Stormw.	PointSource	Transb.	Algae	
Nemunas	NO3	20988	5002	2	874	15809	0	42676
Venta	NO3	2787	539	0	104	161	0	3591
Lielupe	NO3	3350	2666	0	6	25	0	6047
Dauguva	NO3	432	186	0	9	8	0	636
Nemunas	Ntot	21165	5008	2	2198	16219	3005	47597
Venta	Ntot	2861	542	0	588	306	1377	5673
Lielupe	Ntot	3486	2667	0	144	79	2054	8430
Dauguva	Ntot	444	187	0	77	11	467	1186
Nemunas	PO4	302	23	0	122	309	0	756
Venta	PO4	47	3	0	20	3	0	73
Lielupe	PO4	71	4	0	1	1	0	77
Dauguva	PO4	6	2	0	2	0	0	10
Nemunas	Ptot	312	23	0	124	316	270	1045
Venta	Ptot	50	3	0	20	18	99	189
Lielupe	Ptot	81	4	0	1	6	180	273
Dauguva	Ptot	7	2	0	2	0	52	63

Fig. 25. Distribution of riverine N-NO3 loads in LT river network, t/year. 2000-2010.

Fig. 26. Distribution of riverine N_{tot} loads in LT river network, t/year. 2000-2010.

Fig. 27. Distribution of riverine P-PO₄ loads in LT river network, t/year. 2000-2010.

Fig. 28. Distribution of riverine P_{tot} loads in LT river network, t/year. 2000-2010.

The results of nutrient source apportionment indicate the following:

- The agricultural diffuse source may be regarded as the most important for riverine nitrogen loads (around 45% of total). It is important also for phosphorus (28%).
- The riverine N loads originated from background pollution is less than 1/3 of those of agricultural origin (similarly, around 1/15 for P).
- The transboundary pollution is rather essential despite the retention in the rivers (especially for Nemunas RBD). It constitutes from 22% of riverine P loads to 26% of riverine N loads.
- The auxiliary algae loads form a rather important share in the riverine nutrient loads varying from 11% of N to 38% of P total loads.
- The pollution from urban stormwater is negligible.

2.2.7. Methodology for normalisation of nutrient loads

The riverine load normalisation is applied to the time series of the measured or calculated riverine loads to eliminate the variability related to the hydrometeorological factors – namely, the river discharge. Multiple methodologies are considered in EuroHARP (2007c). We propose the approach from HELCOM (2009).

The methodology includes the following steps:

1. Calculation by the water quality modelling system for the selected time period and

calculation of the time series of yearly nutrient (N-NO₃, N-tot, P-PO₄, P-tot) loads from each of the Lithuanian river basic districts.

2. Calculation of linear regression relation for logarithms of nutrient loads and river discharges

$$\log (L_i) = a + b * \log (Q_i)$$

Here L_i is riverine nutrient load and Q_i is the river discharge in the i -th year, a and b are regression coefficients fitted by the least square method.

3. The normalised riverine nutrient load L_{i-norm} for the i -th year is calculated as

$$\log (L_{i-norm}) = \log (L_i) * (a + b * \log (Q_{mean})) / (a + b * \log (Q_i))$$

Here Q_{mean} is the mean annual river discharge.

4. The normalisation of the riverine nutrient loads is performed for each nutrient in each river basin district.

2.2.8. Calculation of normalised riverine nutrient loads

The methodology of Section 2.2.7 was applied for the calculation of the normalised riverine loads of nitrates, total nitrogen, phosphates and total phosphorus for 4 river basin districts of Lithuania. Calculation was performed for time period 2000-2010.

Fig. 29. Time graph of annual river discharge, riverine N-NO₃ loads, and normalised riverine N-NO₃ loads from Nemunas river basin district. Years 2000-2010.

The time graphs of river discharge, annual riverine nutrient loads, and annual normalised riverine nutrient loads for Lithuanian river basin districts are shown in Figs. 29-44.

The following trends may be identified:

1. There is a pronounced correlation of riverine nitrate, total nitrogen loads and discharge in Nemunas RBD. Load normalization reveals that there is no trend in

2000-2010.

2. There is a pronounced correlation of riverine nitrate, total nitrogen loads and discharge in both Venta and Lielupe RBD.
 - a. Nitrate load normalization for both RBDs reveals significant load increase in 2006 with gradual decrease afterwards.
 - b. Total nitrogen load normalization for both RBDs reveals significant load increase in 2006 with gradual decrease in 2007-2009 followed by sharp rise in 2010.

Fig. 30. Time graph of annual river discharge, riverine N-NO3 loads, and normalised riverine N-NO3 loads from Venta river basin district. Years 2000-2010.

Fig. 31. Time graph of annual river discharge, riverine N-NO3 loads, and normalised riverine N-NO3 loads from Lielupe river basin district. Years 2000-2010.

Fig. 32. Time graph of annual river discharge, riverine N-NO₃ loads, and normalised riverine N-NO₃ loads from Dauguva river basin district. Years 2000-2010.

Fig. 33. Time graph of annual river discharge, riverine N_{tot} loads, and normalised riverine N_{tot} loads from Nemunas river basin district. Years 2000-2010.

3. The correlation of riverine nitrate, total nitrogen loads and discharge is weak in Dauguva RBD. Load normalization reveals no trend.
4. There is a pronounced correlation of riverine phosphate, total phosphorus loads and discharge in Nemunas and Lielupe RBDs. Load normalization reveals that there is a decrease of normalized loads from 2003/2005 to 2008 followed by load increase during 2008-2010 in both RBDs.
5. There is no correlation between the discharge and P loads in Venta RBD (slope parameter $b = 0,09 - 0,12$ comparing to $0,9 - 1,6$ for other RBDs). Therefore normalised riverine loads almost match the non-normalised ones. However one may consider more or less gradual decrease of normalized loads from 2000 to 2008 followed by load increase in 2008-2010.

6. There is a correlation of riverine phosphate, total phosphorus loads and discharge in Dauguva RBD. Load normalization reveals no trend.

Fig. 34. Time graph of annual river discharge, riverine Ntot loads, and normalised riverine Ntot loads from Venta river basin district. Years 2000-2010.

Fig. 35. Time graph of annual river discharge, riverine Ntot loads, and normalised riverine Ntot loads from Lielupe river basin district. Years 2000-2010.

Fig. 36. Time graph of annual river discharge, riverine Ntot loads, and normalised riverine Ntot loads from Dauguva river basin district. Years 2000-2010.

Fig. 37. Time graph of annual river discharge, riverine P-PO4 loads, and normalised riverine P-PO4 loads from Nemunas river basin district. Years 2000-2010.

Fig. 38. Time graph of annual river discharge, riverine P-PO4 loads, and normalised riverine P-PO4 loads from Venta river basin district. Years 2000-2010.

Fig. 39. Time graph of annual river discharge, riverine P-PO4 loads, and normalised riverine P-PO4 loads from Lielupe river basin district. Years 2000-2010.

Fig. 40. Time graph of annual river discharge, riverine P-PO4 loads, and normalised riverine P-PO4 loads from Dauguva river basin district. Years 2000-2010.

Fig. 41. Time graph of annual river discharge, riverine Ptot loads, and normalised riverine Ptot loads from Nemunas river basin district. Years 2000-2010.

Fig. 42. Time graph of annual river discharge, riverine Ptot loads, and normalised riverine Ptot loads from Venta river basin district. Years 2000-2010.

Fig. 43. Time graph of annual river discharge, riverine Ptot loads, and normalised riverine Ptot loads from Lielupe river basin district. Years 2000-2010.

Fig. 44. Time graph of annual river discharge, riverine P_{tot} loads, and normalised riverine P_{tot} loads from Dauguva river basin district. Years 2000-2010.

2.2.9 Decision support method for critical nutrient source areas and nitrate sensitive areas

This chapter covers the work completed under the activity 2.5 (Objective 2.2.3.). The aim of this Activity was to develop a GIS Decision Support Method (DSM) for identification of critical nutrient source areas and sensitive nitrate areas presented in the technical documentation. The developed methodology was applied and the results are presented in a set of maps (Annex III) as well as submitted with this report in electronic format.

This chapter will first briefly introduce the EU legal framework covering the topics related to this Activity. It will then provide a short assessment of the available methodologies for the designation of the critical source areas and sensitive nitrate areas and provide the description of the proposed DSM and the results of the methodology application.

2.2.9.1. European Legal Framework

Water Framework Directive (WFD) (2000/60/EC) sets targets for improvement of water quality as well as requires analysis of the various risks to the water quality resulting from human activities (Article 5 and Annex II), including nutrient loss from agriculture. Moreover, in order to achieve the goals on water quality, defined by the EU legal acts, implementation of carefully targeted cost-effective site-specific measures is required.¹ These measures are integrated into the River Management Plans, which are to be developed and implemented under WFD (Articles 13-14, Directive 2000/60/EC).

One of the widely used methods for identification of specific target areas for implementation of the water pollution reduction measure is designation of critical source areas. Critical source areas (CSA) can be generally defined and the area of higher risk of pollutant runoff, where the majority of contaminants are lost and which, therefore, carry greater responsibility for deterioration of the water quality in a watershed.² Primarily, CSAs can be characterised by the large inputs of the nutrients as well as hydrological activity of the area (increased runoff, erosion, channel processes).³

The Council Directive of 12 December 1991 concerning the protection of waters against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources (the **Nitrates Directive** 91/676/EEC) aims to protect water quality across Europe by preventing the nitrates from agricultural sources from polluting both ground and surface waters and promoting good farming practices. The Directive has to be read in conjunction with the above-discussed Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC), as the Nitrates Directive is an instrument for protection of waters specifically from agricultural pressure.

In order to achieve the general aim behind the Nitrates Directive, the several steps of implementation of the Directive can be identified:

¹Doody, D.G., Archbold, M., Foy R.H. and Flynn, R. (2012) Approaches to the implementation of the Water Framework Directive: Targeting mitigation measures at critical source areas of diffuse phosphorus in Irish catchments. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 93, 225-234.

²Heathwaite, A. L., Quinn, P. F. and Hewett, C.J.M. (2005) Modelling and managing critical source areas of diffuse pollution from agricultural land using flow connectivity simulation. *Journal of hydrology*, 304, 446-461.; Panagopoulos, Y., Makropoulos, C., Baltas, E. and Mimikou, M. (2011) SWAT parameterization for the identification of critical diffuse pollution source areas under data limitations. *Ecological Modelling*, 222 (19), 3500-3512.; Srinivasan, M.S. and McDowell, R.W (2009) Identifying critical source areas for water quality: 1. Mapping and validating transport areas in three headwater catchment in Otago, New Zealand. *Journal of Hydrology*, 379 (1-2), 54-67.

³Heathwaite, A. L., Quinn, P. F. and Hewett, C.J.M. (2005) Modelling and managing critical source areas of diffuse pollution from agricultural land using flow connectivity simulation. *Journal of hydrology*, 304, 446-461.

1. Identification of polluted and threatened waters in pursuance with Article 3(1) of the Directive. Under the framework of the Directive, the term *pollution* refers to “discharge, directly or indirectly, of nitrogen compounds from agricultural sources into the aquatic environment, the results of which are such as to cause hazards to human health, harm to living resources and to aquatic ecosystems, damage to amenities or interference with other legitimate uses of water”. The Directive determines a set of minimum criteria that can be used for identification of polluted/threatened surface waters, groundwater, and eutrophic / possibly eutrophic freshwater bodies, estuaries, coastal waters and marine waters. In relation to surface waters the polluted / threatened waters are the ones containing or the ones that could contain a concentration of more than 50 mg/l of nitrates. The same limit value applies to groundwater, while eutrophic bodies are determined in accordance with their level of eutrophication.
2. Designation of nitrate vulnerable zones (NVZs). A vulnerable zone refers to an area of land, which drains into the waters identified as polluted or threatened in accordance with the abovementioned criteria (as set in Article 3(1) of the Directive), thus contributing to the nitrate pollution in the particular body of water. Yet the Directive provides a possibility for Member States to be exempt from this obligation by establishing and applying vulnerable-zones action programmes throughout the whole national territory, hence treating the whole territory as a vulnerable zone. Vulnerable zones have to be reviewed every four years, and the Commission has to be notified on any revisions or additions.
3. Establishment of Code(s) of good agricultural practices. Codes of good agricultural practices have to be established by Member States and implemented by farmers on a voluntary basis. The Code has to contain provisions covering at least the issues identified in the Annex II A of the Directive. In addition, in order to promote the application of code(s), Member States shall establish, where necessary, a programme encompassing such measures as training of farmers and provision of information.
4. Establishment of Action Programmes for implementation by farmers, whose lands are located within NVZs. Unlike Codes of good agricultural practices, Action Programmes are compulsory. They include measures, already provided in the Codes (which become mandatory in the NVZs) and measures prescribed by the Directive (Annex III).
5. Monitoring and reporting to the Commission. Member States have to carry out national monitoring and deliver reports to the Commission every four years. The reports shall cover such issues as concentration of nitrates in freshwaters, eutrophication, vulnerable zones, and assessment of Action Programmes.

The description above provided a brief insight in the general legal framework and implementation obligations in regards to surface waters’ pollution from agricultural sources. Further chapters will focus on more specific issues, namely – designation of critical source areas and nitrate sensitive areas.

2.2.9.2. Designation of Critical Source Areas

In order to develop a sophisticated DSM as required under the objective 2.2.3., the assessment of available methodologies for designation of both critical source areas and nitrate sensitive areas has to be carried out. In relation to the assessment of methodologies on critical source areas, the situation is rather complex, as there are no particular common European guidelines for designation of such areas, therefore, the assessment of CSAs designation will be based on the available literature. After the assessment of available literature, the most appropriate methodology for designation of CSAs will be developed.

2.2.9.2.1. DESCRIPTION OF CRITICAL SOURCE AREAS DESIGNATION METHODOLOGIES

While such paradigm as critical load⁴ is widely used in the EU environmental air quality policy context, there is no officially adopted definition of CSA in relation to water quality, neither are there any common methodologies or criteria developed for identification of CSA in the EU. Consequently, the definition and designation of the CSA to a great extent is subject to data availability and level of assessment⁵.

In the view of the WFD, which commits EU Member States to a significant improvement of water quality as well as establishment of measures for the improvement and control of water quality, development of the methodologies for targeting the essential water quality improvement measures⁶ is necessary. A number of methodologies are proposed for identification of CSA. Sivertun and Prange⁷ suggest that the soil erosion model, such as universal soil loss equation (USLE) can be used in identification of the CSA. Such tools as Phosphorus Index (PI), topographic index (TI), normalised vegetation index (NDVI) approach, curve number (CN) model,⁸ Nutrient Export Risk Matrix (NERM), SCIMAP, P Indicator Tools (PIT) and other methods are also used for identification of CSA by different authors⁹. These methodologies vary significantly in their approach, definition and description of key processes, complexity and resources required for its implementation¹⁰.

Among the available methodologies index methods are most commonly used in identification of CSA or the area of the highest potential risk of nutrient loss¹¹. Although such methodologies do not generally allow for identification of the amount of nutrient loss and represent the relative contribution of an area to the overall nutrient loss, such methodologies use widely available information and are relatively simple. Generally, the concept of the index models is based on attributing an area a relative rank of vulnerability¹². This can be achieved through application of the relatively simple, quasi-physical model, which takes into account basic key characteristics of the area contributing to the water pollution¹³.

So far index methodologies were applied in identification of CSA in the USA, Denmark, Sweden, Norway, England, Australia and New Zealand. However, there are several issues

⁴ Defined as “a quantitative estimate of an exposure to one or more pollutants below which significant harmful effects on specified sensitive elements of the environment do not occur according to present knowledge” (UNECE)

⁵ Supra note3

⁶ Heckrath, G., Bechmann, M., Elholm, P., Ulen, B., Djodjic, F. & Andersen (2008). Review of indexing tools for identifying high risk areas of phosphorus loss in Nordic catchments. *Journal of Hydrology*, 349, 68-87.

⁷ Sivertun, A. and Prange, L. (2003) Non-point source critical area analysis in the Gisselo watershed using GIS. *Environmental Modelling and Software*, 18(10), 887-898.

⁸ Shang, X., Wang, X., Zhang, D., Chen, W., Chen, X. and Kong, H. (2012) An improved SWAT-based computational framework for identifying critical source areas for agricultural pollution at the lake basin scale. *Ecological Modelling*, 262, 1-10.

⁹ Supranote 1

¹⁰ Supra note 6

¹¹ Drewry, J.J., Newhan, L.T.H. & Greene, R.S.B. (2011). Index models to evaluate the risk of phosphorus and nitrogen loss at the catchment scales. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 92, 639-649.

¹² Supranote11

¹³ Supranote3

related to the application of the index methods in identification of CSA of nitrate and phosphate in the context of the present assignment. First, index methods are traditionally and widely applied in the definition of CSA of P losses, while there is only limited evidence of application of such methodology in designation of CSA of N losses¹⁴. This can be partially explained by the difference in main parameters influencing P and N losses¹⁵. Consequently two different approaches will have to be applied in identification of CSA of nitrate and phosphate losses within this project. A second issue is related to the scale of application of index models – originally this approach was developed for the analysis on the level of field or small catchment¹⁶. Assessment on such scale requires a certain quality and precision of input data, and consequently application of such methodologies on a much larger scale (i.e. country level) might have certain implications and will have to be interpreted with caution.

As stated previously, identification of CSA of P and N is often performed by different methodologies, and therefore the following literature review will separately assess the two possible approaches.

P index methodology is by far the most commonly used methodology for definition of the CSA of phosphate loss¹⁷. The original P index was developed in the US to assist farmers and producers in identification of the measures for reduction of P losses¹⁸. The original approach accounted for transport factors (i.e. soil erosion, surface runoff, topography, soil hydraulic conductivity) as well as for source factors (i.e. soil P content, P application (manure and fertilisers) and method)¹⁹. The discrete (often arbitrary) values presenting the above mentioned parameters were added together to obtain the overall P index. Subsequently transformed P indices source and transport factors were multiplied in order to better represent the landscape processes. However, it is recognised that P index methodology must be further adapted in each particular situation to account for the regional geographic and climatic conditions²⁰. For instance, Danish P index incorporates subsurface drainage parameter, since in Denmark soil erosion and surface runoff were shown to have relative low impact of P loss, while subsurface runoff constitutes a significant factor²¹. Additionally, Danish P index takes into account different soil types' P binding capacities and the resulting P leaching capacities. In Norway P index takes into account regular freeze-thaw conditions, which might result in the significant P releases from plant residues as well as snow and snow melt related P losses²². Each P index provides different index value interpretation, generally classifying the areas into low, medium, high and very high risk areas.

In case of N loss, distance to the stream and topography were not found to be as important as such factors like soil permeability and source factors (e.g. background values and N

¹⁴ Supra note11

¹⁵Supranote3

¹⁶Supranotes3,11

¹⁷Supranote11

¹⁸Heathwaite, L., Sharpley, A. & Bechmann, M. (2003).The conceptual basis for a decision support framework to assess the risk of phosphorus loss at the field scale across Europe. *Journal of Plant Nutrients and Soil Science*, 166, 447-458.

¹⁹Supranote18, 6

²⁰ Supra note 18

²¹Supranote6

²² Supra note 18

inputs)²³. Nevertheless, identification of the CSA of N loss is a complex task and factors as nutrient input amounts and methods, soil type, climate, topography, hydrology, land use and land management type might play an important role in the process of nitrate loss²⁴.

Taking into consideration the complexity of the processes associated with the pollutant loss, distributed or semi-distributed hydrological models are often used in identification of CSAs. SWAT (Soil and Water Assessment Tool) is one of the most widely applied models.²⁵ There is a number of issues associated with utilisation of the SWAT model in designation of the CSAs, such as inability of routing the runoff across catchments, disregard of distance from the runoff areas to water bodies, and amount and quality of data necessary for modelling.²⁶ Furthermore, it is argued²⁷ that currently there are no tools that would be able to faultlessly determine runoff of pollutants from the fields. Moreover, according to Shang et al.²⁸, due to the well-mixed river model parameterisation in SWAT model, it is particularly difficult to identify original source of major pollutant loads, and thus also - individual CSA within a watershed. Additionally, Doody et al.²⁹ suggests that due to the general gaps in the understanding of the processes associated with CSA (particularly N losses) and insignificant availability of the necessary data, pollution reducing measures should be applied throughout the specific catchments, rather than to a particularly identified CSA. The authors argue that the adequate designation of CSA for further implementation of targeted pollution reduction measure requires more detailed micro-scale modelling, assessment of area characteristics, as well as stakeholder consultations. Nevertheless, taking into consideration that topography and distance to streams is considered as relatively insignificant factor in relation to the CSA of N loss³⁰, methods of determination of such areas, including those based on the application of SWAT models, can be utilised to identify relative pollution risks associated with a particular area or catchment.

Identification of the CSA also requires definition of thresholds of risk, exceeding which an area can be recognised as CSA. Unfortunately, currently there is only limited knowledge available on the critical loads of nutrients, which can be received by the various surface water ecosystems. Moreover, nitrate and phosphate concentration threshold defined by the relevant EU Directives (WFD (2000/60/EC), Nitrate Directive (91/676/EEC) and Directive on the quality of water intended for human consumption (98/83/EC)) are relatively high, and arguably do not provide sufficient framework for necessary improvement of the water

²³ Supra note 3

²⁴ Supra notes 3 and 11

²⁵ Panagopoulos, Y., Makropoulos, C., Baltas, E. and Mimikou, M. (2011) SWAT parameterization for the identification of critical diffuse pollution source areas under data limitations. *Ecological Modelling*, 222 (19), 3500-3512.; Doody, D.G., Archbold, M., Foy R.H. and Flynn, R. (2012) Approaches to the implementation of the Water Framework Directive: Targeting mitigation measures at critical source areas of diffuse phosphorus in Irish catchments. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 93, 225-234.

²⁶ Supra note 1

²⁷ Ibid.

²⁸ Supra note 8

²⁹ Supra note 1

³⁰ Supra note 3

quality.³¹ Besides, identification for specific nutrient load thresholds on a country or even smaller scale will require significant additional research. Literature suggests various approaches to definition of thresholds. Pamagopoulos et al. (2011) used threshold values proposed by the national classification system. Rodriguez et al., (2011) compared actual nutrient loads with the loads under the baseline scenario, which corresponds to the pre-defined optimal manure and fertilizer application conditions. However, actual choice of thresholds is generally driven by the economic reasons, i.e. costs of implementation of targeted pollution reduction measures³². In such circumstances definition of the CSA is widely based on the statistical analysis of nutrient losses generated (e.g. in kg/ha/year) by individual areas within a study area (e.g. sub-catchment, catchment or country) and utilising arbitrary selected classes and thresholds. For instance, the simplest statistical analysis of definition of CSA based on deviation from the average nutrient load within the study area can be used.³³

2.2.9.2.2. DESIGNATION OF CRITICAL SOURCE AREAS: METHODOLOGY

The proposed methodology for identification of the critical source areas (CSA) is based on the methodology review presented above and takes into consideration the available data, its quality and level of precision³⁴. CSAs of N and P losses are identified using two different methodologies.

CSAs of P losses

As shown in the literature review, methodologies based on the P index principle are most commonly used in identification of the CSA of P losses. This can be explained by the relative simplicity of this approach, general availability of the data necessary for the calculations and interpretation. For the same reasons the methodology proposed for the designation of the CSA of P losses in the context of this project is based on the same approach, in particular, Pennsylvania P index³⁵ and Danish P index³⁶ (see Table 12). Pennsylvania P index is one of the best recognised and widely used and here is used as the framework. Taking into consideration the characteristics of Danish topology, low intensity of rainfall regime and moderate soil erodibility in Denmark Pennsylvania P index was modified to account for these country-specific factors. Danish P index contains parameter which takes into account the impacts of different soil types' P leaching potential and stresses impact of subsurface drainage on the P losses³⁷. According to Heckrath et al. (2008) amendments, which make this index more suitable for implementation in the conditions of European Nordic countries including Lithuania. Application of this methodology on the country level requires further modifications and adjustments driven by the scale and availability of data. Figure 45 presents the decision tree describing the process of the CSA of P losses designation.

Similarly to the other P indices the proposed methodology consists of two main parts: source factors and transport factors. Although the original P indices also include the screening part, for this particular methodology this part is excluded due to the scale of the evaluation and

³¹Isermann, K., and R. Isermann. 2003. “Unavoidable” in contrast to “tolerable” emissions/losses of reactive compounds of carbon (C), nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and sulphur (S) stemming from the total system nutrition and its immissions into the surface waters. Book abstracts from the European conference of coastal zone research: An ELOISE Ap-proach, 5th ELOISE Conference, Gdansk University of Technology (Poland), 24-27 March 2003. p. 117-118.

³²Supranote8

³³Supranote7

³⁴Supra note2

³⁵Supra note18

³⁶Supra note6

³⁷Andersen, H.E. and Kronvang, B. (2006). Modifying and evaluating a P index for Denmark. *Water, Air, and Soil Pollution*, 174, 341-353.

inability to incorporate field-by-field soil screening.

Table 12. Differences in phosphorus indexing approaches: Pennsylvania P index, Danish P index, proposed P index

	Pennsylvania P index	Danish P Index	Proposed P index
Screening Tool	Yes (soil P test, contributing distance)	Yes (soil P test, contributing distance, subsurface drainage type)	No (absence of data on soil P test)
Source factors			
Soil P test	Yes	Yes	No (no sufficient data available)
Fertilizer P rate	Yes	Yes	Yes (combines both)
Manure P rate	Yes	Yes	
P source application method	Yes	Yes	No (no sufficient data available)
Manure P availability	Yes	Yes	No (no sufficient data available)
Transport factors			
Erosion	Yes	Yes	Yes
Leaching potential	No	Yes	Yes
Runoff potential	Yes	Yes	Yes
Contributing distance	Yes	Yes	Yes
Modified connectivity	Yes	Yes	No (no data with sufficient level of detail available)

Source factors are represented by the input of P in the form of animal manure and fertilisers expressed in P kg/ha. Also here the soil P test and adjustment of P input according to the application methods is ignored due to the difficulty of accurately predicting these factors on the country scale. Consequently Source factor can be calculated as follows:

$$\text{Source factor} = \text{Manure rate} + \text{Fertiliser rate (kg/ha)}$$

Transport factor plays particularly important role in definition of the P losses from the agricultural fields. Using the combination of Pennsylvania and Danish P indices, the proposed metrology has the following elements of the transport factor: erosion, runoff potential, leaching potential, subsurface drainage, and contributing distance. See Table 13 for details and factor arbitrary classification. Transport factor is calculated applying the following formula:

$$\text{Transport factor} = (\text{Erosion} + \text{Runoff potential} + \text{Subsurface drainage} + \text{Leaching potential} + \text{Contributing distance}) / 22$$

Finally, P index can be calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{P index} = 2 \times \text{Source factor} \times \text{Transport factor}$$

In practice, interpretation of the P index will be driven by the cost of the measures necessary to reduce P losses from the areas identified as CSA. Table 14 presents the interpretation of the developed P index. This classification is adopted from the original Pennsylvania P index. In the context of Lithuania this classification method might require field calibration and further adaptation to suit the local circumstances as well as taking into consideration potential costs

and other policy requirements.

Figure 45. Decision tree describing the process of the CSA of P losses designation.

Table 13. Elements of Transport Factor and their arbitrary classification.

Element	Classification				
Erosion (tonnes ha⁻¹)	Soil loss ((tonnes ha ⁻¹ year ⁻¹)				
Runoff potential	0	2	4	6	8
	Very Low	Low	Medium	High	Very High
Subsurface drainage	0		1		2
	No artificial drains		Ditch		Tile drainage
Leaching potential	2		4		6
	Sandy soil		Loamy soil		Organic soil
Contributing distance	8			0	
	Under 45 m to water course			Over 45 m to water course	

Table 14. P index interpretation.

P index value	Class
< 60	Low
60 – 80	Medium
80 – 100	High (potentially CSA)
> 100	Very High (CSA)

Figure 46. P index Source factor – fertiliser and manure application data used in SWAT model.

All the data, necessary for application of the proposed methodology, is generally available and can be produced easily, while all calculation can be performed using GIS software.

Figure 47. P index Transport factor – Erosion data obtained from the SWAT model.

Methodology application

The proposed methodology is used to identify CSAs of P losses in one sub catchment in Lithuania (Nevėžis catchment, River Kruostas) to demonstrate the applicability of the proposed methodology.

For the Source factor P input data from the SWAT model was used (Figure 46).

Erosion data was taken from the SWAT model output (USLE methodology -The universal soil loss equation (Williams,1975)) on HRU level and converted to the 10 m grid (Figure 47).

Runoff potential and leaching potential were calculated from the soil data available and used in the SWAT model (see Table 16). Leaching potential is based on classification of all soils into sandy, loamy or highly organic (Figure 48). Runoff potential estimation is based on the soil permeability classification and slope (Figure 49). Since runoff potential and soil permeability data were not available in the Lithuanian soil data base for the selected catchment, these parameters were estimated based on the available literature (see Table 16). It is important to note that special attention has to be paid when using soil classification and related methodologies from different countries, since soil classification, in particular

textural classifications, vary significantly between the countries³⁸. Based on the classification presented in Table 16 and methodology presented by the US Department for Agriculture, surface runoff classes were defined for the soil within the studied catchment (Table 15).

Figure 48. P index Transport factor – Leaching potential defined by soil type.

Contributing distance classes were calculated based on the distance to a particular area from the water courses (Figure 50).

Subsurface drainage was defined using the Lithuanian drainage survey data. All territories with drains were assigned class value of 2 as having a greater potential of P losses. Areas with ditches were assigned a value of 1 and areas with no drainage were given a value of 0 (Figure 51).

After calculating source factor, transport and P index, the values of P index were classified based on the principle presented in Table 14.

The maximum calculated P index value in the studied sub catchment was 36.25 which according to the original Pennsylvania index classification can be defined as “Low”. Consequently, no area could be designated as risk areas based on the present interpretation (see Figure 1 of Annex III). However, it must be noted that applying the proposed methodology on the country level as well as performing cost-benefit analysis of the potential

³⁸ Booth, C. A., Fullen, M. A., Jankauskas, B. & Jankauskiene, G. (2003). International calibration of the textural properties of Lithuanian EutricAlbeluvisols. Soil Science and Agrochemistry, Nr 4.

pollution reduction measures might help in definition of a different P index values interpretation approach which will better suit Lithuania.

Figure 49. P index Transport factor – Runoff potential determined by soil permeability and slope.

Table 15. Runoff potential classification

Slope %/Soil Permeability Class	Rapid and Very Rapid	Moderately Rapid	Moderate	Moderately Slow	Slow	Very Slow and Impermeable
< 1	Very Low	Very Low	Very Low	Low	Medium	High
1 – 5	Very Low	Very Low	Low	Medium	High	Very High
5 – 10	Very Low	Low	Medium	High	Very High	Very High
10 – 20	Very Low	Low	Medium	High	Very High	Very High
>20	Low	Medium	High	Very High	Very High	Very High

Figure 50. P index Transport factor – Contributing distance determined by the distance from the water course.

Figure 51. P index Transport factor – Subsurface drainage obtained from drainage survey data.

Table 16. Data and classifications used in determination of runoff potential and leaching potential

Grain-size composition ^{39,40,41}	S-s1/s	Ps/s	Ps/s/p, ps/s/p2-m	Ps/p-p1	p/p-p1	p-p1/p2-m, p-p1/m	P2/m	Ps/p2-m	Organic Soils
Particle Size classification (according to N.A. Kachinsky) ⁴²	Coarse sand	Medium sand	Fine sand	Coarse silt	Coarse silt	Medium silts	Fine Silt	Clay	
Leaching potential value (Danish P index)	2					4			6
Hydraulic Conductivity, m/hr ⁴³	6.34*10 ⁻¹ (sand)	5.63*10 ⁻¹ (loamy sand)	1.24*10 ⁻¹ (sandy loam)	2.27*10 ⁻² (sandy clay loam)	2.27*10 ⁻² (sandy clay loam)	6.12*10 ⁻³ (silty clay loam)	8.82*10 ⁻³ (clay loam)	4.62*10 ⁻³ (clay)	
Permeability speed, m/hr ⁴⁴	Rapid and Very Rapid	Rapid and Very Rapid	Moderately rapid	Moderate	Moderate	Slow	Slow	Slow	Moderate
	1.52*10 ⁻¹ – 5.08*10 ⁻¹	1.52*10 ⁻² – 5.08*10 ⁻²	1.52*10 ⁻² – 5.08*10 ⁻²	1.52*10 ⁻² – 5.08*10 ⁻²	0 – 1.52*10 ⁻³	1.52*10 ⁻² – 5.08*10 ⁻²	0 – 1.52*10 ⁻³	0 – 1.52*10 ⁻³	
Soil Type ⁴⁵									Peat and other highly organic soils
Drainage Characteristics ⁴⁶									Fair to Poor

³⁹Gatuliene, M. & Krepstiene, O. (2006) AUGALININKYSTĖS PAGRINDAI, Parengta pagal „Ūkininkavimo pradmenų“ mokymo programą.

⁴⁰Volungevicius, J., Eidukeviciene, M. & Prapiestiene, R. (2006) Assessment of grain-size composition spatial structure for Lithuania's Pleistocene surface deposits by statistical grid method. *Geologija*, 55, 55-65.

⁴¹ Example of soil grain size classes defined in the Lithuanian soils data base.

⁴²Ukraine National Agricultural University, Department of Soil Science and Soil Conservation (2008). Soil Science: Practical Methods Manual – Methodologica Instruction Book for the Undergraduate students of Agronomy and Ecology.

⁴³ Clapp and Hornberger (1978) in RESRAD Manual: 5 Hydraulic Conductivity. Available from: <http://web.ead.anl.gov/resrad/datacoll/conduct.htm>

⁴⁴US Department for Agriculture, Surface Runoff Index Classes. Available from: <ftp://ftp-fc.sc.egov.usda.gov/VA/soils/surfacrunoff.pdf>

⁴⁵Unified Soils Classification System, Military Soil Engineering Field Manual 5-410 (1997). (used for highly organic soils)

⁴⁶ Supra note 45

CSAs of N losses

As stated in the presented literature review, the mechanisms driving N losses from the fields are relatively poorly influenced by the topology and distance to watercourse⁴⁷. Moreover, there is little information available on simple and affordable methods for identification of CSAs of N losses⁴⁸. Therefore, it is reasonable to use the output of the SWAT model, developed under the present contract, in order to identify CSAs of N loss on such a large scale as a whole country. In this case the N output values per HRU, provided by the SWAT model, take into consideration not only information on the N input data, but also soil parameters, landuse type, and precipitation, which are important factors in determination of the N losses.

Figure 52 presents the decision tree describing the process of the CSA of N losses designation.

First, the results of the surface water quality modelling, i.e. nutrient (nitrate) loads (expressed in kg/ha/year) for each modelling unit (Hydrological Response Unit) are obtained. These values represent nutrient load reaching the watercourses within a particular watershed, taking into consideration parameters characterising input of the nutrients including diffuse pollution from agricultural sources, point-source anthropogenic pollution, natural background nutrient loads and transboundary pollution. Additionally, nutrient load values integrate data on the hydrological processes governing the total nutrient leaching volumes, e.g. soil parameters, climate data and topology. Such approach to representation of nutrient loads reflects the need for combination of the nutrient input data with the hydrological processes characterisation, which is necessary for more accurate identification of the CSAs⁴⁹.

Second, information on the nutrient loads per HRU is statistically analysed⁵⁰. Outliers and HRUs with the N loads equal to zero are excluded in order to ensure that these values do not impact the results. Additionally, all HRUs identified by the SWAT model as non-agricultural territories are also excluded. This is done in the view of the general purpose of the current contract and the particular need of reduction of diffuse N pollution from the agricultural land.

Third, N loads are divided by the HRU area in order to obtain the value of N kg/ha/year.

Forth, criteria for designation of the CSA and definition of potential risk areas must be selected. As stated in the presented literature review, the selection of the designation thresholds is mainly determined by the potential cost of the pollution risk reduction measures to be implemented throughout the defined CSAs. Taking into consideration the high standard deviation characteristic for the N load data at HRU level produced by SWAT model developed with this project (mean = 5.70, STD = 49.52) (Table 17), it is suggested that the use of percentiles is the most appropriate approach for defining CSA and potential risk areas. In this case CSA are defined as HRUs with N loads exceeding 90th percentile, while HRUs with loads exceeding 75th percentile are considered as areas of potential risk (Table 18).

Table 17. Analysis of the N loads at HRU level

Average	STD	Median	Mode	50th percentile	75th percentile	90th percentile
5.696107	49.51926	0.330651	170.6061	0.330650587	0.903012774	2.879085247

⁴⁷ Supra note 3

⁴⁸ Supra note 11

⁴⁹ Supra note 3

⁵⁰ A minimum requirement would be elimination of zero values and value equals to infinity, however, other more complex statistical methods such as Chauvenet's criterion, Grubbs' test for outliers, Peirces's criterion can be performed.

Figure 52. Decision tree describing the process of the CSA of N losses designation.

Methodology Application

The method described above was implemented in order to demonstrate the applicability of this method in the context of Lithuania using the available data and the result of the PAIC-SWAT modelling, produced within the framework of this project. This chapter will shortly

describe the result of this method’s application as well as identify the issues encountered in the process. See Annex III for maps representing the results of CSA designation.

Table 18. Matrix representing criteria for designation of CSAs and potential risk areas

Type of designation	Critical Source Area	Potential Risk Area
Statistical criteria		
Between 75 th percentile and 90 th percentile		
Above 90 th percentile		

After the compilation of data and statistical analysis of the nutrient load areas 41,484 HRUs were left for the analysis. Later, 90th and 75th percentile were calculated – equal to 2.88 and 0.90 respectively. Consequently, CSAs and potential risk area were defined (see Figure 2 of Annex III). Analysis of the results shows that 9,849 ha are designated as CSAs of N loss, while 81,219 ha can be defined as potential risk areas. It can be seen that the pattern of CSA and potential risk areas distribution somewhat matches the results of the water quality modelling (Figure 4 of Annex III).

2.2.9.3. Designation of Nitrate Sensitive Areas

Following the similar approach as the one used in the determination of CSA designation methodology, also the methodology for designation of nitrate sensitive areas has to be developed after a careful scrutiny of available data. Before turning to the assessment of the available methodologies, it has to be noted that the term “nitrate sensitive area” is used in two occasions in the European context. First, there are Member States that use this term for the purpose of the Nitrates Directive – instead of “nitrate vulnerable zone” – applying all of the NVZs requirements to the NSAs. Second, the term is also used in the framework of the Urban Waste Water Directive (Directive 91/271/EEC), where nitrate sensitive areas partly correspond to the NVZs, and their designation methodologies overlap at some instances. Taking into consideration that the current project is mostly focusing on diffuse pollution from agriculture, the notion of NSA that will be used in the following paragraphs is associated with the Nitrates Directive, not Urban Waste Water Directive.

The following chapters will first of all analyse the available data on designation of Nitrate Sensitive Areas. After the analysis of available methodologies, the most appropriate methodology will be developed specifically for Lithuania based on the available data, legislation and the conditions in Lithuania.

2.2.9.3.1. DESCRIPTION OF NITRATE SENSITIVE AREAS DESIGNATION METHODOLOGIES

As it was already noted above, the Directive provides two options in relation to designation of NSAs, consequently the EU Member states can be generally divided in two groups – those who designate particular NSAs, and those, who mark the whole territory as vulnerable. For the purpose of the current task, the methodologies of countries designating particular NSAs for surface waters will be observed in a more detail.

Nevertheless, taking into consideration, that the Directive provides just general requirements in relation to designation, the methodologies differ from one EU Member State to another. The paper will first of all describe the specifics of a number of Baltic Sea region countries, proceeding with the description of selected methodologies in other European countries. As the terms “nitrate vulnerable zone” and “nitrate sensitive area” may be interchangeable in the

context of the Nitrates Directive, both of them will appear in the following paragraphs (depending on a country).

Estonia

Currently in Estonia there are two adjacent NVZs - Pandivere zone and Põltsamaa-Adavere zone. The area of Pandivere has been designated as State Water Protection Area already in the Soviet times, due to pollution of water caused by intensive development of agriculture in 1974-1985; during the designation of NVZ it was just extended, thus covering a larger territory, but still being primarily based on the Soviet designation.⁵¹

The most recent methodology for review of NVZs encompasses a variety of issues, including, area of agricultural land, number of farm animals and “IPPC farms”, fertilizer use, geological conditions, soils, surface water monitoring data.⁵² The gathered data is being analysed by the group of selected experts, as there are no particular national indicator values or formulas developed for NVZs designation purposes.

Latvia

Implementation of NSAs designation requirement in the Republic of Latvia was carried out in the framework of Latvian Ministry of Environmental Protection and Regional Development / Danish EPA, DANCEE project “Transposition and Implementation of EU - Nitrates Directive”. The measurements of Latvian surface waters indicated that none of the water objects had the concentration of nitrates that would exceed the limit values as determined by the Directive (i.e. > 50 g/ml); yet due to the lack of knowledge on nitrate concentration in groundwater, a separate methodology for designation of NSAs was developed.

Taking into consideration the advices of Danish experts, it was decided to designate the vulnerable zones considering *inter alia* the following aspects: statistics of agricultural activities and GIS modelling of meteorological and geological conditions. Currently the NSAs are designated according to the model⁵³ - in lines of administrative boundaries -, regarding the above-noted aspects. Even though this method is not developed in accordance with the requirements of the Directive, the EC has approved it as an initial approach towards the designation of NSAs.

Poland

In Poland the designation of the NVZs has been mainly based on the pollution of surface waters, following the hydrological borders of catchments.⁵⁴ Yet very few catchments of sensitive waters are actually situated in the NVZs, suggesting that the designation of NVZs has to be improved, making a closer link with the identification of sensitive waters.⁵⁵ The Polish example depicts the situation, where even though the general procedures go along with the Directive’s requirements (i.e. the nitrates concentration value of 50 mg/l), the actual situation indicates a need for a more reasonable designation methodology, which would fill in the existing gaps between the NVZs and sensitive waters.

Czech Republic

The Water Act of the Czech Republic clearly delineates what is a vulnerable zone. Section 33 provides that “vulnerable zones are areas of occurrence a) of surface water or groundwater, used or designated, in particular, as a resource of drinking water, in which the nitrate concentration exceeds the value of 50 mg/l or which may reach this value or b) of

⁵¹ Report of Estonia on the implementation of Nitrate Directive 2000 - 2003.

⁵² Töövõtuleping 4-1.1/287, Nitraaditundliku ala (NTA) laiendamise vajaduse analüüs.

⁵³ Method developed by Dr. V. Jansons from Latvia University of Agriculture.

⁵⁴ Assessment of the Designation of Nitrate Vulnerable Zones in Poland, Contract 2006/441164/MAR/B1

Implementation of the Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC) Task 3, November 2007

⁵⁵ Ibid.

surface water in which the water quality is or may be undesirably impaired due to high nitrate concentration from agricultural sources”. Accordingly, in addition to the Directive’s required 50 mg/l limit value, the Czech Republic takes more precautionary approach, providing a legal ground for designation of vulnerable zones in territories considered as generally vulnerable to pollution, even in cases, where the data on actual pollution is lacking.⁵⁶

The review of vulnerable zones is performed in accordance with the Government Order No. 103/2003 Coll. The review is carried out by professional institution, designated by the Ministry of the Environment after the assessment of findings of monitoring the quality and quantity of surface water and groundwater, data taken from the quality monitoring of the withdrawn water, and data on the quality of withdrawn raw water monitored by operators of water supply systems. The review is carried as prescribed – at regular intervals not exceeding 4 years.

England and Wales

The most recent methodology for assessment and review of NVZs in England and Wales has been introduced in 2012. Methodology developed specifically for designation of NVZs for surface waters is rather elaborate, being comprised of eight steps, which are described in a detail in the Method Statement⁵⁷.

The first step encompasses the identification of surface freshwaters for analysis. After the surface water catchments have been identified, the relevant surface water quality monitoring data has to be analysed. The purpose of the statistical analysis is to determine, whether “the 95th percentile nitrate concentrations observed at each monitoring site exceeded 50 mg/l” or whether “the 95th percentile nitrate concentrations at each monitoring site was predicted to exceed 50 mg/l in 2015 based on trends”. Step three involves land use modelling of nitrate pollution, which not only enables to carry out the assessment without monitoring sites and provides confidence in statistical analysis conclusions, but also identifies the significance of agriculture’s contribution. The evidences from previous two steps are combined in step four to judge whether or not a water body was subject to nitrate pollution. When polluted surface waters are determined, the next step is to identify land draining to these waters; the draining is identified based on the location of monitoring site on the water body and subject of the model prediction. Following step is dealing with the identification and exclusion of monitoring sites, where nitrate pollution is localised and/or has a relatively large non-agricultural contribution. In addition the existing surface water NVZs are assessed for inclusion or removal from NVZ designation (step seven). The last stage of designation is focused on forming workshops for review of preliminary results that mostly concentrates on the catchments with less certain data.

The abovementioned process depicts the most recent methodology on the review of NVZs. As the designation of NVZs in England and Wales was carried out already four times before, the methodology has undergone some noteworthy changes, and the area covered by NVZs has increased with each review. If in 2002 the review of surface waters was based solely on the analysis of water quality monitoring data, then in 2008 England already started to distinguish land-use sources of nitrates, applying an empirical model.⁵⁸ The accumulation and development of previous approaches slowly evolved into the present one.

⁵⁶Report of the Czech Republic. Status and Trends of Aquatic Environment and Agricultural Practice According to Article 10 and Annex V of Council Directive 91/676/EEC Concerning the Protection of Waters Against Pollution Caused by Nitrates from Agricultural Sources, 2008.

⁵⁷Method Statement for Nitrate Vulnerable Zone Review – Surface Waters.Environment Agency report to Defra and Welsh Government – supporting paper for the Implementation of the Nitrates Directive 2013 – 2016. April 2012.

⁵⁸ Ibid.

DESIGNATION OF NITRATE SENSITIVE AREAS: METHODOLOGY

The proposed methodology for designation the NSA based on the quality of the surface waters in Lithuania primarily takes into consideration the designation criterion defined by the Nitrate Directive. Secondly, the methodology draws upon the experience of other EU Member States in development and application of different methods for designation of the NSA.

As outlined in previous chapters, according to the Nitrate Directive, the main criteria for designation must be the current and perspective quality of the surface waters. Therefore, NSAs are defined as territories that drain into polluted or potentially polluted surface waters, where nitrate (nitrous compound) concentration exceeds 50 mg/l. Moreover, Nitrate Directive underlines that NSAs have to be reviewed every four years, taking into consideration the last available water quality information and scientific and practical knowledge on nitrate water pollution from agricultural land. However, in the EU Directive 75/440/EEC on the quality of surface water intended for the abstraction of drinking water in the Member States the threshold of 25 mg/l is set as the recommended (guidance) value. Therefore, the current methodology will define this lower threshold as an indicator of potential nitrate sensitive area.

The short analysis of the experience of the EU Member States in development and application of NSAs designation methodologies shows that until recently only few countries have developed and applied methodologies fully compliant with the Nitrate Directive. Methodologies that address most of the issues set by the Directive in relation to the NSAs designation present a combination of the water quality monitoring data analysis and hydrological modelling for estimation of the nitrate pollution loads and water quality in all the water bodies in the country. One of the most elaborate methodologies for NSAs designation based on the surface water quality was developed in England for the 2012 NSAs review and is described in part 2 of this paper.

This chapter will present the proposed NSA designation method based on the surface water quality for Lithuania. This methodology combines the best practice from the EU Member States and takes into consideration the comments and recommendations of the relevant EU institutions.

The proposed method consists of 7 main phases:

- 1) Identification of water bodies;
- 2) Collection and analysis of the water quality monitoring data
- 3) Collection, interpretation and analysis of the results of the modelling of nitrate pollution of surface waters based on the yearly nutrient loads;
- 4) Definition of water bodies that are subject to nitrate pollution (above 50 and 25 mg/l);
- 5) Definition of agricultural lands draining into the earlier defined polluted surface waters (NSA and potential NSA);
- 6) Screening of the selected NSA for contribution of non-agricultural sources to the pollution of the relevant water body;
- 7) Taking into consideration the results of the screening process, finalisation of the NSA designated area.

The general outline of the designation process is presented in Figure 53. Each phase of the method is described below in a detail.

Figure 53. Outline of the NSA designation process.

Phase 1. Identification of water bodies

At this phase all the water bodies are defined and identified.

When combining monitoring and modelling results, the water bodies are defined as the modelling units, i.e. the Hydrological Response Units.

Phase 2. Collection and analysis of the water quality monitoring data

In the second phase the available data on surface water quality is collected and analysed. Water quality data from all the national monitoring sites and other potentially useful water quality data is collected.

First, the available monitoring data is analysed in order to assess its completeness, consistency, and quality; outliers are identified and eliminated⁵⁹. If the amount and consistency of data allows (minimum of 19 measurements are necessary during the review period), values above the 95th percentile must also be excluded from the analysis in order to avoid inclusion of the measurement data, which characterises extreme weather conditions such as storms.

Second, the location of the water monitoring stations and sampling sites is identified and geographical database is created.

Third, the type of the monitoring site location is determined at added to the geographical database. For the purpose of this analysis two types of the monitoring site locations are differentiated:

- a) Tributary site: monitoring site located in the water body that has no upstream catchments;
- b) Main water body site: monitoring site located in the water body that has one or more upstream catchments.

Further, all monitoring sites are classified according to the nitrate (nitrogenous compounds) concentration, that is - all the monitoring sites are classified according to the data on site passing and failing the water quality threshold defined in the Nitrate Directive: concentration of nitrate of 50 mg/l and recommended threshold of 25 mg/l. The following classes are presented in Table 19.

Table 19. Monitoring data classification.

Data characteristics	Class
Threshold exceeded at least once during the review period: 95th percentile concentration is ≤ 50 mg/l	Fail (NSA)
Threshold exceeded at least once during the review period: 95th percentile concentration is ≤ 25 mg/l	Fail (potential NSA)
No exceedance of threshold	Pass

⁵⁹ Outliers can be identified using various statistical methods including Chauvenet's criterion, Grubbs' test for outliers, Peirces's criterion.

Phase 3. Collection and analysis of the SWAT modelling results

In this phase the results of the surface water quality modelling are collected and interpreted for their further application for the designation of the NSAs.

The results of the surface quality modelling are analysed on two levels:

- 1) Water body level – individual water body level only,
- 2) Catchment level – catchment including all water bodies upstream.

Modelling results are used for identification of nitrate concentration in all water bodies in the country including water bodies that do not have water quality monitoring sites. Based on the modelling results all water bodies in the country are classified according to the nitrate concentration at different levels of confidence.

Phase 4. Identification of all polluted water bodies

At this stage the results obtained in Phases 2 and 3 are combined in order to identify all the water bodies in the country that are subject to the nitrate concentration above the thresholds of 50 mg/l and 25 mg/l. Precautionary principle is applied in this process and the following is applicable:

- 1) In situations, where confidence levels demonstrated by the monitoring data and modelling results were different, the worst of two water quality indicators was selected.
- 2) Similarly, in the situations, where results of monitoring and modelling were contradicting, it was assumed that the worst of two levels of water pollution must be assumed until the further evidence is available.
- 3) Where the results of modelling or monitoring did not give more than 50% of confidence⁶⁰ on their own, then combination of two was assumed to increase the confidence of the information regarding water body quality status, i.e. of nitrate concentration being above or below the threshold of 50 mg/l (or 25 mg/l).
- 4) Finally, when only one of the sources of water quality data (monitoring or modelling) did not provide any information on a particular water body status, the other source was considered as true.

In accordance with the Nitrate Directive, this process is performed for two scenarios:

- 1) Current water quality (base year, e.g. 2010);
- 2) Potential water quality: predicted water quality (based on statistical and other types of modelling).

Phase 5. Identification of the agricultural land draining into the polluted water bodies to be designated as NSAs

The first step of Phase 5 requires identification of the agricultural land draining into the polluted water bodies defined in Phase 4. This is done based on the results of the

⁶⁰Confidence levels can be determined using standard statistical methods, such as T test, which require a certain size of sample.

hydrological model of the water quality.

Further the identified agricultural lands are assessed for their potential designation as NSAs. This is done taking into consideration the type of monitoring site (tributary or main water body) and level of modelling (water body or catchment) that indicates the exceedance of the nitrate concentration threshold. See Figure 52 Phase 5 for the decision tree for selection of NSA designations. The following main principles are applied in this process:

- 1) If monitoring site indicating the exceedance of the nitrate concentration threshold is a tributary site, then only agricultural areas draining into the relevant polluted water body are designated as NSAs;
- 2) If monitoring site indicating the exceedance of the nitrate concentration threshold is a main water body site, then agricultural areas draining into the relevant polluted water body, as well as areas draining into all water bodies upstream of the relevant polluted water body are designated as NSAs;
- 3) If monitoring site is not present in the water body, then the results of the water quality modelling are examined:
 - a) If model predicts exceedance of the nitrate concentration threshold at the level of water body, then only agricultural areas draining into the relative polluted water body are designated as NSAs;
 - b) If model predicts exceedance of the nitrate concentration threshold at the level of catchment, then agricultural areas draining into the relevant polluted water body, as well as areas draining into all water bodies upstream of the relevant polluted water body, except for the non-polluted main water bodies with monitoring sites, are designated as NSAs.

Phase 6. Screening of the selected NSAs for contribution to pollution from non-agricultural sources

Taking into consideration the experience of EU Member States on designation of the NSAs, and relatively large number of appeals against the designation decisions, it is considered necessary to assess the potential contribution of the non-agricultural pollution sources to the concentration of nitrates in the water bodies, which adverse water quality was the reason for designation of the NSAs.

Phase 6 presents a screening process for identification of areas and water bodies where impact of non-agricultural pollution could significantly influence the decision for designation of the NSAs. The main steps of the screening process are described below. See Figure 52 for the decision tree of the screening process.

- 1) Using the data provided by the water quality model, the distance from the monitoring sites to the upstream (point) non-agricultural pollution sources is calculated. Monitoring sites with an upstream (point) non-agricultural pollution source located within 500 m are selected for further screening.
- 2) Available information on the (point) non-agricultural sources are analysed in order to assess the mixing zone of these point sources.
- 3) If the monitoring site is located within the mixing zone of the point source, monitoring site might be significantly impacted by the point-source discharge. In this case more detailed analysis and micro-level modelling might be required for assessment of the proportional impact on the water quality of various sources of pollution. EU practice

suggests that agricultural contribution of 17% is considered as not insignificant (European Court of Justice Case C 221/03, Belgium) and can still lead to designation of the NSA.

- 4) If monitoring site is located outside the mixing zone, some additional checks can be performed in order to assess the potential impact of the non-agricultural point source to the pollution of the relevant water body.
 - a) High concentration of ammonium can be an indication of a significant impact of effluent discharge. Analysis of the nitrate concentration excluding ammonium might help to identify the impact of the effluent discharge. If nitrate concentration excluding ammonium still exceeds the threshold (50 mg/l or 25 mg/l), then agricultural pollution represents the greatest burden on the water at this monitoring point and designation of relative NSA can be confirmed. If no, additional analysis explained in point 3 has to be performed.
 - b) Peak nitrate concentrations during the summer months indicate the potential significant impact of the point source discharge at the relevant monitoring site. If this is the case, additional analysis explained in the point 3 has to be performed. Otherwise, agricultural pollution sources play a major role in deterioration of water quality at this monitoring site and therefore designation of the relevant NSA can be confirmed.

Phase 7. Finalisation of the NSAs locations

Taking into consideration the screening process, performed at the Phase 6, the final list of NSAs is developed.

Methodology Application

The method described above was applied to show the potential issues related to implementation of this method in the context of Lithuania, taking into consideration data availability and the result of the SWAT water quality modelling, produced within the framework of this project. This subchapter presents the result of this method's application. See Annex III for maps representing the results of the designation of nitrate sensitive areas (i.e. NSAs).

The first issue, encountered in the process of NSAs designation, was the poor availability of the water monitoring data. In order to define 95th percentile, at least 19 measurements are necessary for the review period. In Lithuania maximum of 12 measurements per year are done at one particular monitoring site; a large number of sites has maximum of 4 measurements per year. Besides, in year 2010 only 177 monitoring stations had 4 and more measurements, which results in the country coverage that is not sufficient in its extent for the designation of NSAs. Consequently, decision has been made to use the monitoring data for the period 2007-2010 in order to increase the coverage of the country by the monitoring site with 4 and more measurements in 4 years⁶¹. Moreover, since the majority of the monitoring sites did not have 19 or more measurements in 4 years, it was impossible to calculate the 95th percentile – therefore maximum values were used in this analysis instead. This is a significant drawback, since extreme value resulting from, e.g. extreme weather events, were not filtered out from the assessment.

⁶¹ Period of 4 years was selected as matching the NVZ review period, i.e. EU Nitrate directive requires reassessment of Nitrate Sensitive Areas (or Nitrate Vulnerable zones) to be performed every 4 years.

Another issue, related to the low data coverage, was encountered at Phase 5. Often the designation of the catchment upstream of the failing monitoring site, using the monitoring results from the monitoring site upstream of the failing monitoring site, was deemed impossible, since monitoring data at two stations did not match in terms of the measurement period (e.g. different year of monitoring). In such case the precautionary method was used and the relevant upstream areas were designated as NSAs.

Analysing modelling data, the decision was made to use the monthly average values representing water quality in a particular river. This was done due to the specific characteristics of SWAT model, which is not best fitted for the prediction of the water quality on the day-to-day level. Consequently daily average values were substituted by the monthly averages, in order to improve the potential of comparison between such modelling results and single threshold exceedance cases, identified through onsite measurements.

At Phase 6 the distance to the nearest point-source (affluent discharge) was assessed. Four failing monitoring sites were identified as located in the vicinity of point-source pollution discharge. The proportional contribution of different pollution source types was assessed for the catchments of relevant failing monitoring sites. This assessment showed that agricultural sources contributed the major part of the pollutant to the total nutrient loads within this catchment and therefore the designation of the relative areas was confirmed. The final results of the designation process are presented in Figures 3, 4 and 5 of Annex III.

Figures 5 and 6 show that designation of the NSA based on the monthly average modelling results identifies fewer NSA than analysis of the monitoring results. This can be explained by the fact that average modelling results do not allow for capturing of all the possible single threshold exceedance events. Besides, monitoring data from 4 years was used, which could significantly increase the potential for single measurements exceeding the thresholds. Some discrepancies in the identified NSA can be explained by limited availability of the monitoring data. This consequently indicates the advantages of using a combination of monitoring and modelling results in identification of NSA.

4. Concluding remarks and compliance with the Working Plan

Recommendations for future development of modelling system

Limited recommendations for the future development of modeling system and methods in regard to the calculation of nutrient load, retention, source apportionment of riverine loads and load normalization may be concluded from the study performed within this stage

1. We recommend to establish a routine data exchange related to the modelling input data for transboundary catchments with neighbouring countries on annual basis.
2. Alternative calibration of SWAT setup for only N and P load calculation (without usage of Qual module for stream processes) might be recommended due the linkage of SWAT with Qual module seems to undergo serious improvements in SWAT community. Such a recommendation provided in ELLE&PAIC (2012a) is related also to unaccounted loads of nutrients via algae transport into reaches.
3. The routine use and update of the modelling system with actual input data should be performed. We recommend to do this on annual basis.
4. We recommend continuous work to increase the performance of the model and its input data sets. The results of load, retention and source apportionment calculation may be checked subbasin-by-subbasin to indicate input data problems. These results may be used in combination with the monitoring data. The systematic review of input data issues may be performed for the locations where the observations indicate outlying values from the modelling results and/or sudden changes in the time series.

Recommendations for the future application and development of DSM

Taking into consideration assessment of the available methodologies as well as issues encountered during the application of the two DSM described in this chapter the following recommendations can be made regarding the future application and developed of the DSM aimed at designation of the critical source areas and sensitive nitrate areas.

1. It is necessary to improve the availability and quality of the monitoring data. Such improvements might include increased frequency of samplings, particularly in the regions identified as areas at risk from the water pollution. Besides, sampling times must be aligned at different monitoring sites in order to facilitate such measurement data utilisation in the NSAs designation screening process. Moreover, increased number of samples will permit calculation of 95th percentile and hence allow for exclusion of the extreme values from the monitoring data analysis.
2. Identification the country specific pollution thresholds might require detailed assessment on the impact of different pollutants of various habitats and ecosystems. Therefore, it is advisable to carefully identify critical loads specific for various habitats and ecosystems found in Lithuania.
3. With the development of scientific knowledge and understanding of the processes governing N losses from the agricultural fields it might be important to incorporate transport factors in the assessment of CSA of N losses.
4. Identification of CSA of P losses could be further improved by incorporation of the cold climate factors such as snow runoff and freeze-thaw P losses. Moreover, flooding frequency and precipitation factors could be incorporated. Source factor could be

improved by integration of soil test results and manure and fertiliser application type factors. Finally, as any model methodology of designation of CSA of P loss could be improved through the use of data of higher quality and field calibration and testing of its performance.

Compliance with working plan

The second phase of the project has been implemented in full compliance with the work schedule proposed in the Technical Proposal and confirmed by the Contract.

Submission of the second Interim Report has also corresponded to the work schedule and was submitted in timely manner, i.e. July 31, 2012.

Table 20. Activities, milestones, deliverable and reports during Stage II of the project.

Week	Activities	Milestones	Deliverables	Reports
21-22	A8			
23	A8, A9			
24	A7, A8, A9			
25-28	A9	M6		
29-30	A10			
31-32	A10, A12			
33-34	A11			
35-36	A11, A12	M7		
38	A12, A13			
39-40	A14	M8	D3, D4	12D

Milestones:

M6: Water quality modelling for 2000-2010 accomplished

M7: Task 2 accomplished

M8 Task 3 accomplished

Deliverables

D3: Decision support system, GIS layers

D4: Post-processed results of the water quality modelling

Reports

12D: draft of the 2nd Interim Report

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Annex I – Minutes of technical meeting 3-May-2012

Project on Development of methodics and modeling system of nitrogen and phosphorus load calculation for surface waters of Lithuania (ID No.100054)

Minutes of the meeting

Subject: Technical meeting

Date and place: May 3, 2012, Environmental Protection Agency (A.Juozapavičiaus str. 9, Vilnius)

Participants: Svajūnas Plungė, Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)
Uldis Bethers, SIA “Procesu analizes un izpetes centrs” (PAIC)
Juris Sennikovs, PAIC

Discussed and agreed:

1. Transboundary issues. The Agency will deliver the required data to PAIC.
2. Regionalization issues. MIKE Basin set-ups were transferred to PAIC
3. Experience on application of SWAT in other countries, e.g. Poland, has been shared.
4. General project progress.

Minutes prepared by Uldis Bethers

Annex II – Minutes of technical meeting 27-Jul-2012

Project on Development of methodics and modeling system of nitrogen and phosphorus load calculation for surface waters of Lithuania (ID No.100054)

Minutes of the meeting

Subject: Technical meeting to discuss the progress before submission of the 2nd Interim Report

Date and place: July 27, 2012, Environmental Protection Agency (A.Juozapavičiaus str. 9, Vilnius)

Participants: Svajūnas Plungė, Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)
Uldis Bethers, SIA “Procesu analizes un izpetes centrs” (PAIC)
Juris Sennikovs, PAIC
Oskars Beikulis, SIA “Estonian, Latvian & Lithaunian Environment” (ELLE)
Viktorija Maceikaitė, UAB “Estonian, Latvian & Lithaunian Environment”

Discussed and agreed:

1. Delivery of 2nd Interim Report - next week on Friday (August 3, 2012).
2. Clarification of content of 2nd Interim Report – PAIC has prepared a working document for clarification, namely, the table with description of content of each relevant chapter and issues to be discussed (the table is attached)
3. Upgrade of modeling system and model – description of improvements will be added to one chapter of the report.
4. Calculation of nutrient loads (objective 2.2.2)
 - 4.1. Agreed on 2.4.1.1
 - 4.2. Conception of separation of sources under 2.4.1.2 has been discussed
 - 4.3. PAIC will think about possible solution regarding calculation of retention in wetlands under 2.4.1.3
 - 4.4. Agreements reached on 2.4.1.4 – 2.4.1.10
5. GIS DSM (objective 2.2.3) – the EPA has received a presentation of work methodology and expressed regret that expectations of EPA were not shared before the start of the work
 - 5.1. Activity 2.5.1.1 is completed
 - 5.2. Activity 2.5.1.2 is partially completed and awaiting for input data from PAIC
 - 5.3. Activity 2.5.2.3 is almost completed.

Minutes prepared by V.Maceikaitė

Table of issues for the technical meeting of 27-Jul-2012

Chapter	Progress / contents	Issues
1. Upgrade of modeling system and model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transboundary issue - Regionalisation - Re-calibration to (a) better describe processes and (b) achieve reasonable results at downstream stations 	<p>Shall we (1) describe improvements, (2) re-write manual (3) combine 1&2 – describe improvements and leave manual for Stage III</p> <p>SWAT error w/lakes</p> <p>Delivery of new set-ups</p>
Not in report: PAIC-SWAT upgrade		Delivery of new PAIC-SWAT version
2. Calculation of nutrient loads (2.2.2)		
2.4.1.1.Prepare methodology for the separation of background, non-point agricultural sources and other anthropogenic pollution sources;	<p>Methodology – loads to SW from individual HRUs</p> <p>Agricultural – loads from land use classes “agricultural” and “pastures”</p> <p>Background – loads from land use classes which are not agricultural</p> <p>Other anthropogenic: - loads from “urban” and from point sources – sum of point sources</p>	Whether pastures = agricultural.
2.4.1.2.Calculate yearly nutrient loads (from different sources such as background, non-point agricultural pollution, atmospheric, storm water, settlements not connected to sewage treatment facilities, settlements connected to sewage treatment system, industrial plants and international pollution) to the surface water bodies of Lithuanian river basin districts for time period of 2000-2010;	<p>Background Agricultural Point source International</p> <p>Additional classification Atmospheric = input</p>	<p>Existence of additional classification (which is part of other sources)</p> <p>The point source data base does not include indexes that would allow for separation of different sorts</p> <p>Nomenclature and spatial resolution (sub-basin) of output results</p>
2.4.1.3.Calculate nutrient retention in the surface water bodies of Lithuanian river basin districts for 2000-2010 year period, separating retention in buffer zones, river beds, wetlands, lakes and	<p>According to EuroHARP – if the load is in SW body when retention is in the river system ONLY</p> <p>River/reservoir system - DONE</p>	<p>No “buffer zones” in SWAT SWAT error in calculating mass balance for lakes</p> <p>No intermediate outputs of SWAT to calculate retention in wetlands (some effort</p>

ponds;		may be possible) Nomenclature and spatial resolution (sub-basin) of output results
2.4.1.4.Prepare methodology for the calculation of source apportionment of riverine loads of the loads to the Baltic Sea;	Point Background Agricultural diffuse Transboundary Methodics for follow up of different sources in the river system	
2.4.1.5.Calculate the source apportionment of riverine loads of loads coming to the Baltic Sea for the time period of 2000-2010 by using methodology prepared for the activity 4 of objective 2.2.2.	Done	Nomenclature and spatial resolution (sub-basin) of output results
2.4.1.6. Prepare recommendations/ methodology for the normalization of nutrient loads by eliminating the influence of hidrometeorological factors (weather and water flows) in order to assess the influence of impact of antropogenic activities;	There are various methods. We propose simplest ($Li=Li*Q/Qi$)	OK?
2.4.1.7.Normalized nutrient loads to the Baltic Sea has been calculated (by using methodology prepared for the activity 6) for the period of 2000-2010 in order to evaluate anthropogenic influence;		Nomenclature and spatial resolution (sub-basin) of output results GIS?
2.4.1.8.Evaluate result obtained from activities 2, 3, 5, 7 and provide possible explanations for trends in results;	Chapter in report	
2.4.1.9.Prepare technical manual for the calculation of nutrient load, retention, source apportionment of riverine loads;	Chapter in report	Will be a part of PAIC-SWAT User Manual
2.4.1.10..Prepare recommendations for the future development of	Formal point	

modeling system (model) and methods in regard to activities raised in the objective 2.2.2.		
3. GIS DSM (2.2.3)		
2.5.1.2.Prepare GIS DSM to identify critical nutrient source areas, sensitive nitrate areas and prepare technical documentation for prepared method;	Method1 Method2 Documentation	ELLE
2.5.1.2.Prepare GIS layer (at a scale of 1:50000) and maps in report of critical nutrient source areas and nitrate sensitive areas by using GIS DSM methodology prepared for the previous activity;	Layer1 Layer2 Map1 Map2	ELLE
2.5.1.3.Prepare recommendations for future application and development of GIS DSM methodology (describing application and development possibilities and limitations).	Formal – extension in documentation	ELLE

Annex III - Maps produced in the process of application of CSA and NVZ designation methodologies